

ORISON

innOvative **R**esearch Infrastructure based
on **S**tratospheric ballo**ONS**

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AGU	Aerial Guidance Unit
APL	Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory
ASI	Italian Space Agency
ATC	Air Traffic Control
BDU	Below Deck Unit
BEXUS	Balloon Experiments for University Students
BGAN	Broadband Global Area Network
BIT	Balloon-Borne Imaging Testbed
BLAST	Balloon-borne Large Aperture Submillimeter Telescope
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CCD	Charge Coupled Device
CIGS	Copper Indium Gallium Selenide
CMB	Cosmic Microwave Background
CMOS	Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor)
CNES	Centre National D'Études Spatiales
COTS	Commercial Off The Shelf
CSA	Canadian Space Agency
CSBF	Columbia Scientific Balloon Facility (NASA)
CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion
DC	Direct Current
DGPS	Differential GPS
DLR	German Aerospace Center
DSSS	Direct-Sequence Spread Spectrum
EBASS	Esrange Balloon Service System
EBEX	E and B Experiment (balloon-borne polarimeter)
ECCN	Export Control Classification Number
ETNA	Equipment of TM/TC for Nacelle
EUSO	Extreme Universe Space Observatory

FB	FleetBroadband
FOG	Fiber Optic Gyros
FOV	Field of View
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRP	Glasfiber Reinforced Plastics
HALO	High Altitude Lensing Observatory
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HF	High Frequency
HGA	High Gain Antenna
IP	Impact Point
IR	Infrared
JAXA	Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency
JHU	John Hopkins University
L/D	Lift to drag ratio
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NIR	Near Infrared (>1000 nm)
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NOSYCA	New Operational SYstem for the Control of Aerostats
OBC	On-board Computer
OTA	Optical Tube Assembly
PILOT	Polarized Instrument for Long-Wavelength Observations of the Tenuous Interstellar Matter (ISM)
PoGOLite	Polarized Gamma Ray Observer
QPSK	Quaternary Phase Shift Keying
RC	Ritchey-Chrétien
RHCP	Right-Hand Circularly Polarized
RMS	Root Mean Square
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic

RUDICS	Router based Unrestricted Digital Interworking Connectivity Solution
Rx	Receive
SBD	Short Burst Data
SDD	Solid State Device
SDSS	Sloan Digital Sky Survey
SIP	Support Instrumentation Package
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SOFIA	Stratospheric Observatory for Infrared Astronomy
SPB	Super Pressure Balloon
SSA	Space Situational Awareness
SSC	Swedish Space Corporation
SuperBIT	Superpressure Balloon-borne Imaging Telescope
TBC	To be confirmed
TC	Telecommand
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol
TDRSS	Tracking and Data Relay Satellite System
TEXUS	Technologische Experimente unter Schwerelosigkeit (Technological Experiments under Microgravity)
THISBE	Telescope of Heidelberg for Infrared Studies by Balloon-Borne Experiments
TIFR	Tata Institute of Fundamental Research
TM	Telemetry
Tx	Transmit
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
USD	US Dollar
UV	Ultraviolet (<400nm)
VIS	Visible Wavelength Range (astronomical definition, ~400-1000nm)
WAAS	Wide Area Augmentation System
WASP	The Wallops Arc Second Pointer
ZPB	Zero Pressure Balloon

1 INTRODUCTION

The ORISON project aims to provide a flexible multipurpose platform for stratospheric balloon flights which can be adapted based on the needs of a certain mission, scientific goal, and required instruments. With this desire for great flexibility comes a wide range of requirements that a generalized balloon platform needs to fulfil in order to enable a variety of use cases.

While many desired capabilities are technically feasible, they might turn out to be too expensive to be realized if certain key elements or subsystems need to be developed first. Subcomponents and parts that are commercially available reduce cost and development time of the platform significantly, and influence high level design decisions. It is important to know the market of relevant parts that can be readily procured and adapted for this project not only to determine its general feasibility, but also to come up with a meaningful cost budget. With this in mind, the information gained from our market research will allow informed decisions for systems engineering, but might also trigger reiterations of the project's requirements, scope and goals in order to fit within existing funding frameworks.

2 SCOPE

The aim of this report was to research commercially available parts and / or suppliers for subsystems and elements of the balloon platform that the ORISON study team deemed to be critical. With this in mind, the report aims at providing a number of options and insights that address certain problems in platform systems engineering. The report does not aim at completeness, nor to select any preference or solution to address a given requirement. It shall rather act as a starting point for system engineering purposes. For a detailed platform design, too many open questions remain at this point, and the system's characteristics need to be tailored to a mission profile that has yet to be defined.

The report does not address the mechanical and thermal design of the gondola, as this level of detail is impossible at this point. Any detailed mechanical and thermal design will be driven by the chosen components, and supported by simulations of structural and thermal loads. This is beyond the scope of this report.

3 PLATFORM CONSIDERATIONS

3.1 BALLOON SYSTEMS AND PROCUREMENT

This section will cover several topics with regard to balloons themselves. One part will cover the different materials that have been used for stratospheric balloons, particularly Mylar, Latex, Kevlar, and different kinds of polyethylene plastic. Another one will cover the performance of the balloons, particularly with regard to long duration flights. Furthermore, additional abilities such as manoeuvrability techniques will be discussed.

3.1.1 Sounding Balloons

Sounding balloons are used for meteorological observations, e.g. to measure temperature, humidity and wind speed directions. These balloons are so-called rubber balloons, made from natural rubber latex. The rubber balloon is injected with gas on the ground until partially inflated [1]. The balloon ascends until its bursting point. Typical altitudes for rubber balloons are between 25-40 km, depending on the size, the material and the payload weight.

Typically, these balloons are used for scientific purposes that require low payload masses. When the scientific payloads exceed 15 kg, it is not possible to use single balloons made of latex anymore. Historically, some missions in the 1950s used several latex balloons to obtain more lift power, such as the flight of Audouin Dollfus in 1959. Mr. Dollfus used 104 balloons to lift a telescope in a pressurized capsule. The use of several balloons, if carefully planned, furthermore allows slow descent rates by maintaining one or several balloons intact, providing only little less than the required lift. This can ensure potentially soft landings, which is the reason this technique has been applied for ORISON pathfinder tests, even though it is not the most common technique. The possible durations of these flights are short, from a few hours up to two days (even though there are some exceptions). The main companies that sell latex balloons are Kaymont Balloons (Australia) [2], Hwoyee (China) [3] and Pawan (India) [4]. There are no big differences in their performance, even though according to the specifications the Kaymont balloons can perform at higher pressure differences than the Hwoyee balloons.

3.1.2 Zero-Pressure Balloons

Zero pressure balloons (ZPBs)^a have a venting duct at the base of the balloon, which is why they are also referred to as open to the air. At the balloon base the internal-external pressure difference is zero, which explains how they were named [1]. ZPBs can carry more than 15 kg and use materials which are not necessarily elastic as they minimize the pressure on the balloon film. Historically, one of the main manufacturers of these open balloons was Winzen Research Inc. A few years ago, Winzen merged with another of the classic balloon manufacturing companies, Raven Aerostar [5]. This company has been the main provider for NASA for the last 10 years, and according to the historical data

^a Also referred to as “Ballon Stratosphérique Ouvert” (BSO), i.e. Open Stratospheric Balloon, or Zero pressure Stratospheric Balloons

from Winzen Research Inc, the Winzen balloons were able to take 1.100 kg to 36 km of altitude already in the 1970s.

The performance of the modern balloons can last up to 3 days for conventional flights and up to 55 days for the long duration flights [6].

Figure 3-1: NASA balloon capabilities: Balloon volumes.

Noted in Million Cubic Feet (MCF), (Weight/Altitude Ratio is Approximate) [6]

Another manufacturer is the Space Division of ZODIAC INTERNATIONAL, which is the main provider in Europe, used by CNES, the SSC and Agenzia Spaziale Italiana. This company has its origins in 1896 in the Société Française des Ballons Dirigeables. Currently, their zero pressure balloons can reach altitudes from 20 to 40 km, flight durations of several hours, and up to 3 tons of payload [7]. The material that is used for these balloons is polyethylene. Zodiac also offers a more advanced balloon called Infrared Montgolfière (MIR) that, by the use of aluminium on the top part of the balloon, is capable of keeping helium warmer during the night cycle by reflecting the infrared emission of the ground into the balloon. It thereby reduces the nightly altitude loss caused by lifting gas contraction and eliminates the need of nightly ballast drop to maintain altitude. This kind of balloon can last up to 71 days for payloads with less than 50 kg.

Several space agencies developed their own balloon systems, e.g. JAXA or the Russian Academy of Sciences [8]. There is no detailed information about these balloons available, although they might be of interest in case of a collaboration project. The Russian balloon VAL-120, for example, is able to lift up to 1200 kg to 32.5 km.

The Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (TIFR) in India also performs scientific ballooning with zero pressure balloons and even has been able to get up to 51 km of altitude with a 4 kg payload [9].

Other manufacturers that produce hot air balloons potentially could reconvert their systems to balloons for stratospheric systems. Two of these balloon manufacturing companies are Ultramagic [10] and CabosRegatta [11]. These companies have experience with several materials also used for stratospheric balloons.

3.1.3 Super-Pressure Balloons

Super-Pressure Balloons (SPBs) present a way to reach longer flight times (by obtaining a more stable altitude and thus omitting the daily ballast drop/lifting gas vent cycles). They maintain a higher pressure in the interior of the balloon than the environment. Compared to ZPBs, the balloon envelope walls must have a higher strength in order to withstand the pressure difference. These balloons are used more commonly for long duration missions as they lose less or no lifting gas compared to ZPBs. However, UV radiation causes degradation of the material over time and the stress of the day/night contraction plus possible electrical interactions with the atmosphere can lead to leaks in the balloon film.

The main manufacturers are the same as for the heavy zero pressure balloons, i.e. Raven Aerostar, ZODIAC INTERNATIONAL SPACE DIVISION, and JAXA.

There are some notable differences between these companies that are important to highlight. Raven Aerostar, because of the Google Loon project [15], has made intensive revisions of their manufacturing procedures, quality controls, leak controls and tests at low temperatures to check the performance of their balloons. This has led to Raven now holding the world record of duration of a stratospheric flight with 187 days. This success has been possible through analysis of the balloon design problems and manufacturing processes [12].

Another interesting product is the ultra light polyethylene balloon with 2.8 μm film thickness, developed by JAXA, more specifically the Institute of Space and Astronautical Science. With this new kind of balloon, they have been able to reach an altitude of 53.7 km. This altitude is high enough to access UV regions that are more difficult to reach from 30 or 40 km. However, the maximum payload that currently can be transported to that altitude is 18 kg.

The super pressure balloons of ZODIAC INTERNATIONAL SPACE DIVISION offer flight durations of up to 3 months, at 20 km of altitude, for up to 50 kg of payload.

3.1.4 Manoeuvrability

One of the big challenges of balloon operations is the recovery. Due to fact that weather predictions are only accurate enough for the short term, it is difficult to design detailed flight plans for balloons that take more than 6 hours. However, if a system is used that allows to change altitude of the balloon between different layers of wind, it is possible to control the direction of the flight by making use of different wind directions in these layers. In an extreme case, this method can be used to do station keeping [13] where the balloon can stay above an area of 20 km in diameter.

This technique is available now on some Raven Aerostar balloons that include “ballonet” inside a super pressure balloon that can be filled with regular air to descend, or evacuated to gain altitude.

Another technique is the so-called Boomerang manoeuvre that is employed by JAXA. In this case, the balloon ascends until catching the jet stream winds at approx. 17 km, maintains this altitude for several hours, and then drops ballast, so that the balloon ascends to its full altitude of operation. At this altitude, the balloon will move in the opposite direction. It is theoretically possible to apply similar techniques with almost all ZPBs, and SSC applies related strategies to increase flight durations during semi-annual turnaround conditions over the Esrange Space Center.

3.1.5 Lifting Gas

As one of the non-negligible cost contributions to balloon flights, a short assessment of the lifting gas price shall be presented.

The typical lifting gas used for large scientific balloons is helium. While hydrogen might also be suitable, and the raw product cheaper, helium bears the advantages of easier ground handling, existing equipment and techniques for large balloon missions. The analysis of efforts and costs involved with a complete ground handling system for hydrogen would be beyond the scope of this study. The information provided will thus be limited to helium.

The U.S. Bureau of Land Management lists a price of 3.75 USD/m³ for crude helium to non-government users in fiscal year (FY) 2016 [14]. Based on this number, the resulting costs for filling typical balloon sizes with crude helium are listed in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1: Costs of crude helium for typical balloon sizes, based on prices of the US Bureau of Land Management.

Balloon volume [m ³]	Cost of helium [FY2016 USD]
60,000	1,620
150,000	4,050
400,000	10,799
800,000	21,599
1,000,000	26,998
1,120,000	30,238

A few meteorological agencies use hydrogen in sounding balloons. The use is very limited because of all the necessary safety procedures [15]. It might be worth considering hydrogen as soon as easier procedure for ground handling are established for other purposes [16], especially if the helium price continues to increase.

3.2 GONDOLA STRUCTURE

Within this section, several general considerations concerning the gondola structure will be discussed. With the exception of a short discussion of the availability of standard gondolas for rental, the scope of this section will be mostly limited to the mechanical

structure of the gondola. Platform subsystems, also those responsible for balloon operation, will be covered in the respective sections of this report.

The gondola structure mainly serves the following purposes:

- Provision of a structure to attach the subsystems, instruments, etc.;
- Provision of a mechanical connection point to the balloon;
- Protection of the subsystems and instruments during preparation, transport, ground handling, launch, flight, and landing against mechanical influences;
- If applicable, protection of the subsystems and instruments against light and/or other radiation.

3.2.1 Available Gondola Structures

Since gondolas for larger instruments, particularly for telescopes, are highly specialized for the instrument they carry, they are usually custom made. For smaller instruments, several balloon flight providers offer or are planning to offer standard gondolas that allow the installation of several instruments on a standard mechanical interface. Along with the mechanical interface, typically also certain service interfaces for the instruments are provided in these cases. A list of providers offering standard platforms for small instruments follows. Please note that this list does neither claim to be exhaustive and means to favor the companies listed.

- Swedish Space Corporation (SSC): SSC uses the Medium Erange Gondola (M-Egon) for the BEXUS (Balloon Experiments for University Students) program. The gondola is built to carry a total of 100 kg experiment mass and has physical dimensions of 1.16 m x 1.16 m x 0.84 m. The gondola structure consists of a metal profile frame and standard metal rails for experiment installation. [17]
- Zero 2 Infinity: Zero 2 Infinity is a Spanish company that, among other services, offers flight opportunities for small and mid-sized payloads (under 50 kg) on shared platforms. [18]

Recently, there have also been several attempts on providing multi-purpose pointing gondolas, particularly aiming at applications for astronomy, for larger payloads that would minimize the development effort for single missions. Those are particularly:

- The Wallops Arc Second Pointer (WASP) developed at Wallops Flight Facility, NASA. WASP is a pointing system that can accommodate a payload and can be installed on a gondola. It still requires a gondola structure to be integrated into. WASP is designed to serve payloads of up to 600 kg. [19]
- The CNES Generic Architecture for Multi-mission Pointing Gondolas is a modular gondola system developed by CNES that provides accurate pointing as well as several generic modules necessary for a balloon mission. The architecture includes a generic mechanical design that allows modular design and integration of different payloads and service system modules. The detailed mechanical gondola design so far has differed from mission to mission. The architecture is meant to serve payloads in the mass range between 285 and 1100 kg. [20]

Since both concepts predominantly include the pointing aspects, they are discussed in more detail in chapter 4.

It is worth to mention that some of the balloon flight providers also offer the service of developing and building gondolas for specific payloads. Providers who design and build their own gondolas include CNES (e.g. the generic pointing gondola, see above) and SSC (PoGOLite [21]). Providers who explicitly offer the service of designing and manufacturing gondolas, or of customizing existing gondolas, are the U.S.-based company World View (customization) [22] and the Spanish company Zero 2 Infinity (complete gondolas of up to 2000 kg equipped with payloads) [18].

3.2.2 Gondola Structure Architecture

Different structural architectures have been and are being applied for larger balloon gondolas. Generally, the structural architecture must guarantee sufficient rigidity and strength against deformation or fracture under vibrations and shock, while being lightweight at the same time. Additional points to consider include modularity of structural elements which makes it easy to realize different designs or extend existing ones and, of particular interest for the ORISON platform instruments concept, easy-to-use standard mechanical interfaces for instrument installation. Using industry standard mechanical elements, like aluminum profiles, can be beneficial in these regards.

Figure 3-2 shows several different large gondolas employing different structural architectures.

Table 3-2 furthermore lists the basic structural architectures of several flown gondolas.

Figure 3-2: Previously flown gondola systems.

From left to right, row by row: PILOT gondola [23], CLAIRE gondola [24], SPIDER gondola with installed cryostat [25], EUSO gondola (nadir-viewing) [26], rendering of the EBEX gondola [27], BLAST gondola CAD drawing [28], PoGOLite gondola [21], Sunrise gondola and Sunrise gondola main frame [29], SuperBIT gondola sketch [30], THISBE gondola [31] (images not to scale)

Table 3-2: Previously flown gondolas.

Mission(s)	Flight Provider	Gondola Designer and Manufacturer	Payload	Basic Structural Architecture	Lowest Eigen-frequency [Hz]	Shock Resistance	Gondola Structure Mass [kg]^b	Payload Mass [kg]
PILOT ^c	CNES	CNES	Radio telescope (CMB observations)	Metallic tubes, “ball” connectors	n.a.	n.a.	306 ^d	752 ^d
CLAIRE ^c	CNES	CNES	Gamma ray telescope	Carbon fiber rods	> 10	> 10 g	60 ^f	150 ^d
SPIDER ^g	CSBF	University of Toronto	Radio telescope (CMB observations)	Carbon fiber reinforced polymer tubes with aluminum inserts and aluminum multi-tube joints ^h	> 29	> 10 g vertical, > 5 g lateral	194 ⁱ	1600 ^j
EUSO-Balloon ^k	CNES	CNES	Nadir-pointing UV telescope for cosmic ray detection	Watertight gondola, structure of Fibrolux C GRP profiles, walls of Fibrelam GRP panels ^l . Additional polystyrene sleeve for thermal insulation and buoyancy	n.a.	> 15 g vertical, > 5 g lateral ^m	n.a. ⁿ	n.a.

^b Please note that this mass only refers to the mechanical structure of the payload gondola and may not include service systems, actuators, ballast reservoirs and other elements.

^c All information from [23]

^d Mass figures only apply to payload gondola. Balloon service systems are housed in a separate gondola.

^e All information from [24]

^f Includes gamma-ray telescope structure

^g All information from [25]

^h Aluminum inserts at both ends of the rods for interfacing, multi-tube joints are custom made and also used on BLAST and BLASTPol

ⁱ Outer frame

^j Cryostat

^k All information see [128]

^l Fibrolux profiles are commercial standard profiles available from <http://fibrolux.com>, Fibrelam are commercially available panels.

^m See [128]

ⁿ Total gondola flight mass was 467 kg (excluding balloon service systems which were located in a separate gondola)

EBEX ^o	CSBF	n.a.	Radio telescope (CMB observations)	Aluminum 6061 beams	n.a.	n.a.	676 ^p	2134 ^q
BLAST ^r	CSBF	Empire Dynamic Structures ^s	Submillimeter telescope	Aluminum tubing and I-beams	> 14.4	n.a.	315 ^t	435 ^u
PoGOLite ^v	SSC	Developed by SSC Esrange Space Center	X-ray telescope	Tubular aluminum structure covered in composite honeycomb panels		> 10 g	950 ^w	600
Sunrise ^x	CSBF/SSC	High Altitude Observatory, Boulder	Solar telescope	Aluminum/steel tube framework	ca. 15	> 10 g vertical	n.a. ^y	n.a.
SuperBIT ^z	CSA/CNES	n.a.	Optical telescope	Aluminum honeycomb panels	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a. ^{aa}
THISBE ^{bb}	Univ. of Kiel / CSBF	Dornier-System GmbH (now Airbus DS GmbH)	Optical telescopes	Aluminum tubes		> 10 g vertical	27	80 ^{cc}

^o All information see [27]

^p Outer and inner frame, including support for primary and secondary microwave mirrors

^q Entire scientific payload, excluding CSBF equipment, flight train, and gondola structure

^r All information see [28]

^s www.empireds.com, manufacturing

^t Inner and outer frame structures.

^u Submillimeter mirror, cryostat, electronics on inner frame, cryogenics. Total mass of gondola at launch was 2020 kg, not including flight train and balloon

^v All information see [21]

^w Gondola including power supply, solar panels, communications, and auxiliary equipment (excluding attitude control system)

^x All information see [29]

^y Ca. 2 t total mass

^z See [30]

^{aa} Total gondola mass was ca. 700 kg

^{bb} All information see [31]

^{cc} 80 kg telescope mass. Total gondola flight mass reached 400 kg

3.3 TECHNICAL SYSTEMS AND PROCEDURES FOR PAYLOAD PROTECTION

The most critical parts of a balloon mission in terms of potential damage to the payload thereby are the launch and the landing. This section will cover systems and procedures associated with minimizing the risk of damage during landing.

3.3.1 State of the Art Procedures

The landing and descent sequence of balloon payloads typically consists of the following elements:

- Separation from the balloon
- Descent on a parachute
- Landing

The flight train, including payload, flight service systems, and parachute are separated via a separation command sent by the balloon pilot. For the physical separation, usually pyrocutters are used to cut the suspension line between balloon and parachute. Since the separation from the balloon is critical for a safe landing, usually a redundant system of cutters is installed. In order to avoid free fall in case of unintentional destruction of the balloon, usually a balloon burst detector is installed above the cutter as well which, in such an event, will automatically activate the cutter.

For descent, typically non-steered, circular parachutes are used. These are deployed directly at flight altitude.

Landing typically occurs on a non-steered, either round or cross-shaped, parachute.

Figure 3-3: Sunrise 2 telescope with crush pads (from [32]).

3.3.2 Market Offer of Components

Table 3-3 summarizes the market offer of available parachute systems. Table 3-4 summarizes aspects and providers of shock absorbing materials.

Table 3-3: Available parachute systems.

Type	Manufacturer	Name	COTS	Size [m ²]	Payload mass		L/D ^{dd}	Landing accuracy	Max. release altitude ^{ee} [m]	Max. opening load [g]	Details	Current Application	Mass [kg]	Power [W]	Data	Source
					Min [kg]	Max [kg]										
circular	TBC		TBC	80								BEXUS				[17]
circular	TBC		TBC	100		≈165 ^{ff}						BEXUS	12			[17]
circular	TBC		TBC	120								BEXUS				[17]
cross	Kayser-Threde GmbH / DLR Moraba	European recovery system	TBC	147		450			4,600		2-stage system, first stage: round (7.9 m ²), second stage: cross (147 m ²) deployed at ca. 50 m/s	TEXUS	55.5			[33]
steered parafoil	Airborne Systems	FireFly	yes	95.2	294.8	1089	3.25:1	80% within 150 m of IP ^{gg}	7,468	4.5	Reusable ^{hh} , autonomous guiding, manual overwrite possible	Airdrop	73.5	n.a.	n.a.	[34]
steered parafoil	Airborne Systems	DragonFly	yes	325.2	2222.6	4535.9	3.5:1	80% within 250 of IP	7,468		Reusable, autonomous, manual overwrite possible	Airdrop	230.4	n.a.	n.a.	[35]
steered parafoil	Airborne Systems	FlyClops 2K	yes	≈ 95 ⁱⁱ	340	998	3.25:1	Within 150 m of IP	5,334	4.5	1-time use parachute & AGU	Airdrop	44.9 ^{jj}	n.a.	n.a.	[36]
steered parafoil	Airborne Systems	FC Mini	yes	33.4	92.7	231.8	3.5:1	80% within 100 m of IP	7,468		1-time use parachute & AGU	Airdrop	14.8 ^{kk}	n.a.	n.a.	[37]
steered parafoil	Airborne Systems	MicroFly II	yes	33.4	111.4	226.8	4:1		7,468			Airdrop	34.3 ^{ll}	n.a.	n.a.	[38]
steered parafoil	Autoflug / CIMSA	FASTWing	no	160		3200	> 4:1		7,620 ^{mmm}		two-stage, round stabilization parachute (300 m ²) to reduce vertical velocity			n.a.	n.a.	[39]
steered parafoil	Autoflug / CIMSA	FASTWing CL				6000		100 m ⁿⁿ						n.a.	n.a.	[40]

^{dd} Lift to drag ratio at no wind

^{ee} Above mean sea level

^{ff} Typical approximate BEXUS flight train mass
^{gg} (designated) impact point (IP)

^{hh} Up to ten times

ⁱⁱ Deduced, canopy is modelled after FireFly canopy

^{jj} 32.7 kg canopy, 12.1 kg Aerial Guidance Unit (AGU)

^{kk} 9.7 kg canopy, 5.1 kg AGU

^{ll} 22 kg canopy, 12.3 kg AGU

^{mmm} Highest demonstrated altitude

ⁿⁿ 50 % circular error probability

Table 3-4: Properties and suppliers of shock absorbing materials.

Type	Manufacturer	Name	COTS	Thick-ness [cm]	Crush strength [kN/m ²]	Specific energy absorption capacity [kJ/kg]	Current application	Specific mass [kg/m ²]	Density [kg/m ³]	Source
Paper honeycomb	International Honeycomb Corp.	KF-1-80(0) EDF 51 lb	Yes	10.16	69	3.9	NASA	1.25	12.3	[41]
Aluminium honeycomb	Plascore	CrushLite 0.6	Yes		51.7	3.8			9.6	[42]
Aluminium honeycomb	Plascore	CrushLite 1.4	Yes		172.4	5.4			22.4	[42]
Aluminium honeycomb	Plascore	CrushLite 8.1	Yes		5171	27.8			130	[42]
Aluminium honeycomb	Hexcel	HexWeb 1/4 – 5052 – .0007	Yes		275.8	7.5			25.6	[43]
Aluminium honeycomb	Hexcel	HexWeb ACG – 1	Yes		172.4	5.8			20.8	[43]
Aluminium foam	ERG Aerospace	Duocal 6101-T6 (8%)	Yes		2231 ^{oo}	7.3			214	[44]
Airbags	Airborne Systems		Yes							[45]
Research Results										
Aluminium honeycomb						32 ^{pp}			128	[46]
Styrofoam HD-2						12			72.1	[46]
Epoxy foam						5.5			64	[46]
Balsa wood					11.6 ^{qq}	71.7	NASA space probes		224	[46]

^{oo} Note that for very high crush strength materials, the required surface area of the absorbers becomes quite small, potentially unpractically so.

^{pp} Note that this roughly coincides with a high density, high crush strength commercially available honeycomb structure

^{qq} <http://www.wood-database.com/balsa/>

4 PAYLOAD

The ORISON baseline payload design [47] considers a lightweight telescope with a 0.5 m aperture diameter for observations from UV to NIR wavelengths. Two first-light instruments have been identified:

- 1) a wide field imaging camera with a filter wheel
- 2) a multi-channel imager with high spectral resolution, high cadence, and spectroscopic capabilities

While a flight-worthy instrument design for stratospheric conditions is beyond the scope of this report, the following sections discuss the availability of certain key payload components.

4.1 OPTICAL TELESCOPES

As ORISON aims to be a flexible platform for a variety of instruments, the optical telescope design shall not constitute a limit on an instrument's spectral range. Consequently, a fully reflective telescope has to be chosen. A two mirror Cassegrain reflector with a focal plane behind the primary mirror is an obvious choice, as it allows for compact mechanical designs with reasonably long focal lengths. While the central obscuration of a Cassegrain system might be seen as a small disadvantage, its axial symmetric mirrors are easy to manufacture. Obscuration-free off-axis systems that find use e.g. in some security applications will not be considered here, as they come at a much higher cost.

Most astronomical observatories have adopted the coma-free Ritchey-Chrétien (RC) design, a variant of the Cassegrain telescope where both the primary and the secondary mirror are hyperbolic. The RC seems to be the most practical and versatile choice for ORISON, as it is well corrected over a wider field without any additional refracting elements. Other popular Cassegrain designs such as Corrected Dall-Kirkham (CDK), Schmidt-Cassegrain, Maksutov-Cassegrain, or various fast astrograph designs on the market such as Ricardi-Honders, Harmer-Wynne and its derivatives all use refractive elements that are optimized to relatively narrow spectral ranges where they perform well (usually in the visible); all these designs have therefore been discarded for ORISON to enable applications both towards the UV and the NIR/IR.

A two mirror RC telescope provides the best performance of the widely produced telescope models, and provides the instrument with a beam free of chromatic aberrations; its purely reflective design allows observations at any wavelength (UV - IR). It will be a task of the instrument designer to implement a focal reducer or extender as required for the respective science, detector geometry and wavelength range (UV, VIS or NIR) of the instrument, but these additional refractive elements will then be designed towards the desired wavelength where the respective instrument performs.

Table 4-1 provides an overview of common RC and Cassegrain telescope systems on the market that are offered for groundbased use. Every optical telescope system is usually tailored towards desired system specifications, so this table shall only give some generic overview which designs could act as a starting point. While a gold mirror coating might perform better in the IR, an aluminum coating is still the better and more cost effective choice for a general purpose telescope design.

Table 4-1: Typical RC and Cassegrain systems offered by various manufacturers for groundbased use.

Manufacturer (Country)	Optical Design	Clear Aperture Diameter (mm) Typical f/#	Typical Central Obscuration	Back Focus (mm) (counting from back plate)	Mirror Material	Light Weighted Mirrors?	OTA Structures Offered	Typical OTA Weight (kg) (all OTAs for groundbased use)	
Officina Stellare (Italy)	RC	500 f/8	47%	300	ClearCeram	Conical Shape or Milled Pockets	Carbon truss	85	
		600 f/8	47%	300				105 (130 ^{rr})	
		700 f/8	47%	300				140	
Optical Guidance Systems (USA)	RC	508 f/8.1	36,3%	266,7	"near zero expansion ceramic"	Conical Shape	Tuned Carbon Fiber XZe™ closed tube, carbon fiber truss on request		
		609 f/8	37,5%	292,1					
		830 f/8	35%	250					
	Cassegrain	508 f/16	25%	266,7					
		609 f/16	25%	247,65					
		787,4 f/10	37,5%	247,65					
PlaneWave (USA)	RC	508 f/6.8	39%		Precision Annealed Borosilicate or Fused Silica	Not specified	Carbon truss	63,5	
		610 f/6.5	47%	358				108,9	
Astelco (Germany)	RC	500 f/8	34,4%		Various	Yes, but not specified	As specified by customer (truss, tube)	46 (truss)	
		600 f/8	35%					65 (truss)	
ASA Astro Systeme Austria (Austria)	RC	500 f/8	37,2%	365	Astrositall	No (60 mm thick)	Truss	89	
		600 f/8	37,5%	360				No (70 mm thick)	138
	Cassegrain	500 f/9	36%	365				No (60 mm thick)	89
		600 f/9	33,3%	360				No (70 mm thick)	138
Deep Sky Instruments (formerly RC Optical Systems)	RC	508 f/9.1		255	Astrositall (optionally ion milled), Zerodur		Carbon tube, carbon truss, ruggedized Nomex core	74-83 ^{ss}	
		609 f/9.1		300				140	

^{rr} Weight of the Officina Stellare ProRC 600 OTA of ATUS.

^{ss} Value appears wrong

							carbon fiber sandwich tubes	
Astrosib (Russia)	RC	508 f/8	37,7%		Astrositall, LK-7	No (70mm thick)	Truss	68
Knaeble Engineering (Germany)	RC	500	51%ss	255	Pyrex		Truss	80
Alluna Optics (Germany)	RC	505 f/8	42%	240	Zerodur on request		Truss, tube	79
		550 f/8	42%	235				95
		600 f/8	41%	230				110

Table 4-2 lists companies that have delivered telescopes for balloon-borne, space situational awareness (SSA), military or space applications; this list is not exhaustive. As telescope systems for these applications have been highly customized, one-of-a-kind units, the list shall act as a guideline which vendors have relevant project experience; it is not meaningful to list optical parameters of delivered systems.

Table 4-2: Telescope manufacturers with relevant experience.

Manufacturer	Project Experience
Officina Stellare (Italy)	Telescope for the Balloon-Borne Imaging Testbed (BIT), University of Toronto [48, 49]; new Fine Field Imager optics for SOFIA [50], SSA systems
Optical Guidance Systems (USA)	“JHU/APL’s new solar telescope for balloon borne use” [51]
Deep Sky Instruments (USA)	Ruggedized, military designs, e.g. for extremely fast slewing telescopes; custom instrumentation
Ceravolo Optical Systems (Canada)	Optics for smaller satellite missions [52]
Optical Mechanics (USA)	Custom systems, ruggedized / SSA designs
DFM Engineering (USA)	Custom Cassegrain Systems up to 1.3m aperture diameter

When specifying the telescope, three factors should be especially considered:

a) Mirror material and weight.

In a telescope, the primary mirror is often the single most heavy component. Light weight mirrors have been casted from borosilicate glass (e.g. Schott Borofloat); casting bubble-free mirrors with a surface finish that enables observations at visible wavelengths has been demonstrated at smaller diameters (~300 – 400 mm, [53]), i.e. smaller RC primary mirrors, or secondary mirrors in telescopes. A 60 cm Borofloat mirror weighing only 17 kg has been casted for the Dinium Observatory [54].

However, borosilicate glass has a relatively high coefficient of thermal expansion. Given the harsh thermal environment in the stratosphere, a glass ceramic with a very low coefficient of thermal expansion should be chosen as a mirror substrate to have stable telescope optics independent of temperature (see e.g. Zerodur mirror of the Sunrise balloon telescope, the SOFIA airborne telescope, and various satellite projects). Light weighting of Zerodur mirrors has been demonstrated for up to 90% removal of material [55]. AstroSitall mirrors have been lightweighted up to 70% [56]. Table 4-3 provides an overview of typical “zero expansion” glass ceramics and “low expansion” glasses that find use as mirror substrates in telescopes.

Table 4-3: Comparison of mirror substrate materials with a very low coefficient of thermal expansion.

Trade name	Zerodur	Sitall CO-115M (Astrositall)	Clearceram-Z HS	Ultra-low expansion glass (ULE) Code 7972	Borofloat 33
Company	Schott	Lytkarino Optical Glass Factory (LZOS)	OHARA	Corning Inc.	Schott
Country	Germany	Russia	Japan	USA	Germany
CTE (1/K x 10 ⁻⁹)	0 ± 7 ^{tt}	0 ± 150	0 ± 20	0 ± 30	3250
Temperature Range (°C)	0 ... +50	-60 ... +60	0 ... +50	+5 ... +35	n/a
Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	1.46	1.99	1.52	1.31	1.20
Mean specific heat (J/(kg K))	800	921	773	767	830
Density (g/cm ³)	2.53	2.46	2.55 ^{uu}	2.21	2.2
Type	Lithium aluminum silicate glass ceramic			Titania silicate glass	Borosilicate glass
Light Weighting through	Milling			Casting	
Source	[55]	[56]	[57, 58]	[59]	[60]

^{tt} Expansion Class 0 EXTREME; Standard Expansion Class 0: 0 ± 20 x 10⁻⁹

^{uu} Density not specified in [57], value taken from [129]

-
- b) F- number of primary mirror, and effective focal length of RC.

Especially for a wide field imager, it could be a valuable option to mount the camera in prime focus. The effective focal length of the whole system (M1+M2) defines the resolution in the focal plane.

- c) Athermal structural design

The supporting opto-mechanical structure needs to be free of flexure to ensure reliable pointing, and must provide stable dimensions and alignment over a wide temperature range. A custom carbon-fiber structure seems to be the obvious choice.

4.2 OPTICAL FILTERS

Both first light instruments shall include band pass filters; in particular, the widely adopted Sloan (u g r i z) and “J H K” filter sets have been identified [47]. To achieve a well-defined filter bandpass with high transmission and steep edges, interference filters are used. The definition of the Sloan photometric system [61] excludes the strong airglow line O I X5577 that originates at altitudes above the stratosphere; the Sloan filter bandpass definitions cover the 300 – 1100 nm spectral range, i.e. the sensitivity of Silicon-based detectors. Sloan filters have been widely adopted, which allows a variety of observatories to obtain consistent photometry. In contrast to the Sloan system, no standard definition exists for the often cited JHK bandpasses: Width and center wavelength can vary at each observatory, a dilemma that was discussed e.g. by [62, 63]. The Mauna Kea Observatories near infrared (MKO-NIR) JHK filter set definition [64, 65, 66] has found wider adoption at large professional observatories on dry, high altitude sites, as it was designed towards the atmospheric windows at sites higher than 2 km; however, this bandpass definition turned out to be also not 100% optimal for Mauna Kea [62]. At ORISON flight altitudes, telluric lines up to 2.5 μm are practically absent, and the definition of meaningful “JHK” bandpasses for the ORISON platform has yet to be made.

Table 4-4 gives a guideline on manufacturers that offer filters for astronomical applications. Specifying and building a filter always depends on the spectral response of the detector and the science goals of the instrument; for example, out of band transmission of a Sloan filter beyond 1.1 μm is not critical for a Si CCD or CMOS detector, but can render a measurement with a HgCdTe detector useless. The clear aperture of the filter substrate is defined by the optical design of the instrument. If the filter is placed in a convergent beam, the filter thickness should be chosen such that all filters of a given filter set are parfocal, i.e. a filter change does not vary the focus position. As the filter wheel needs to be a custom design to withstand stratospheric conditions and shock on impact, it will not be discussed in this report.

Table 4-4: Manufacturers of astronomical filters.

Manufacturer	Link / Source, Previous Filter Deliveries
Astrodon (USA)	www.astrodon.com Sloan and narrow-band filters (H- α , O-III, S-II, N-II), substrate sizes > 50 mm feasible on request Note: Sloan bandpasses do not fully match original definition from [61]
Asahi Spectra Co., Ltd. (ASC) (Japan)	http://www.asahi-spectra.com/opticalfilters/astronomical_filters.html Produced, SDSS, MKO-NIR, narrow bandpass, Johnson/Cousins, and other custom filters based on customer specification, also on very large substrates (up to 620 mm)
Schott (Germany)	[67] Custom interference and optical glass filters
Custom Scientific (USA)	http://www.customscientific.com/research_astronomy.html Johnson/Cousins, narrow band H- α , H- β , S-II, O-III, Methane; Custom filters in large sizes (270 mm+) as specified by the customer
Omega Optical (USA)	http://www.omegafilters.com/ Johnson/Cousins, SDSS, JHK, O-II, O-III, S-II, C-II, C-III, H- α , H- β , Custom filters up to 210 mm as specified by the customer
Materion Barr Precision Optics & Thin Film Coatings (USA)	[68] Johnson / Cousins, JHKLM, H- α , O-III, Hale Bopp comet filter set; Custom filters in large sizes as specified by the customer
Finger Lakes Instruments (FLI) (USA)	http://www.flicamera.com/filters/index.html Johnson / Cousins, narrow-band H- α , S-II, O-III up to 65mm square

5 ATTITUDE AND POINTING CONTROL SYSTEM

5.1 BALLOON POINTING SYSTEMS

A crucial part of balloon-borne observatories is the attitude and pointing control system. Typical designs incorporate gimbal systems driven by torque motors for acquiring the desired attitude of the payload. In addition, instead of moving the whole telescope, fast steering mirrors can be added for precise pointing. Sensors such as rotary encoders, magnetic sensors, gyroscope sensors, sun sensors and star trackers determine the attitude. This section discusses necessary sensors and actuators as well as their performance and availability. In addition, two state-of-the-art balloon pointing systems are shortly introduced. A short overview of current or previously flown balloon-borne telescopes and the actuators and sensors for pointing control is given in Table 5-1.

Table 5-1: Comparison of balloon-borne observatories fine-precision pointing systems.

System	Suspension, Actuators		Sensors	Projected Accuracy [arcsec RMS]
	Coarse	Fine		
HALO [69]	3-axis gimbal (WASP + additional axial roll bearing)	active mirror	3-axis gyroscope 4 star tracker rotary encoders	0.04 – 0.06
SuperBIT [30]	3-axis gimbal Reaction wheel + motorized pivot, stepper and dc torque motors	Active mirror (piezo)	3-axis gyroscope 3-axis magnetometer 3 star trackers Rotary encoder	0.02
SPIDER [70, 71]	2-axis gimbal Reaction wheel + motorized pivot, dc torque motor		3-axis gyroscope star tracker differential GPS magnetometers inclinometers sun sensors rotary encoders	50.4
Sunrise [29, 72]	2-axis gimbal Reaction wheel + motorized pivot Linear stepper motor	Active mirror (piezo)	3x sun sensor photovoltaic cells rotary encoders	0.05
BLAST [28]	2-axis gimbal Reaction wheel + motorized pivot dc torque motors		3-axis gyroscope magnetometers inclinometers differential GPS sun sensors 2 star tracker rotary encoders	30
BOOMERanG [73]	2-axis gimbal Reaction wheel + motorized pivot Ball screw linear actuator		3-axis gyroscope differential gps 2 sun sensors rotary encoders	150

5.2 CUTTING-EDGE FINE POINTING SYSTEMS

This subsection gives an overview of the current state-of-the-art high precision fine-pointing systems for balloons, which already include necessary components such as sensors, actuators, and computer and control algorithms. Using existing and flight-proven hardware might reduce development costs and time.

5.2.1 WASP

The Wallops Arc Second Pointer (WASP) is a support system developed at Wallops Flight Facility, NASA. It integrates a two-axis gimballed mechanism with dc torque motors and a gyroscope sensor as well as a star tracker. The main characteristics are listed in Table 5-2 [19]. The system might not be easily available.

Table 5-2: Characteristics of WASP.

Payload Mass [kg]		~600
Payload Dimensions	Diameter [m]	0.5
	Length [m]	8
Accuracy [arcsec RMS]		0.4-0.5

Figure 5-1: WASP Test Flight 1 gondola [19].

5.2.2 CNES Generic Architecture for Multi-Mission Pointing Gondolas

The CNES Generic Architecture for Multi-mission Pointing Gondolas is a modular gondola system developed by CNES that provides accurate pointing as well as several generic modules necessary for a balloon mission. The pointing control system is comprised of a star tracking camera and fibre optical gyroscopes as well as actuators for fine and coarse pointing. CNES offers a complete gondola design and servicing for the

whole mission, including the high-accuracy pointing system. However, this solution might restrict Orison’s flexibility and independence in such a way, that it can turn out unsuitable.

Table 5-3: Characteristics of the CNES Generic Architecture Gondola.

Payload Mass [kg]	285-1100
Payload Dimensions [m]	2 x 1.8 x 2.2
Accuracy [arcsec RMS]	0.5

Figure 5-2: Generic architecture for multi-mission pointing gondolas, CAD model [20].

5.3 SENSORS

The choice of sensors plays a vital role in all pointing control systems, as they determine the pointing precision. The gondola and telescope attitude can be estimated by measuring physical quantities such as the direction of the gravitational or the magnetic field, the relative position of celestial objects, motion of the telescope itself and artificial signals, such as GPS. In the following subsections, typical sensor types are introduced and currently available models listed.

5.3.1 Thermal Requirements

For reliable functioning during flight, selecting sensors suitable for the environmental conditions is important. The systems will be exposed to extreme conditions, such as low pressure and low temperatures. High changes during ascent have to be considered. The overall system design has to ensure that operational conditions are maintained for the whole duration of the mission.

Component temperatures are influenced by a variety of the component's properties, such as surface geometry, emission coefficients and heat sources e.g. electronics, as well as environmental conditions, e.g. incoming radiation from earth and sun, air density and wind.

Atmospheric pressure at 32 km altitude is about 9 millibar (International Standard Atmosphere), thus convective heat exchange plays a minor role compared to conditions on ground. In contrast, temperatures in the tropopause reach -56.5 degree Celsius. The most critical temperature conditions might occur when the balloon passes this layer [29].

5.3.2 GNSS

This section lists some of the main manufacturers for Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receivers and discusses considerations for selecting a suitable device.

Figure 5-3: Trimble NetR9 GNSS receiver [74].

GNSS receivers use satellite signals to determine time and position. The data-precision can be enhanced by using additional information about the signals' inaccuracies. Corrected GNSS signals with measurements of the phase of the signal's carrier wave enable centimeter-level accuracies – as shown in Table 5-4 – and allow the determination of the attitude by using multiple antennas. This technique results in a prediction error of down to 0.1 degrees [75]. The accuracy of attitude information increases with the distance of the antennas. Technologies enhancing the GPS accuracy by such means include differential GPS (DGPS), Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) and real-time kinematic (RTK).

Although often referred to as GPS receivers, most commercially available GNSS modules are capable of processing signals from different global navigation satellite systems, such as GPS, GLONASS, Galileo and BeiDou.

When selecting an appropriate GNSS receiver, limitations of the working range have to be taken into account. Technically, there is no limitation for GPS receivers inside the flight envelope of a high-altitude balloon, however, in accordance with former US Department of Commerce regulations, manufacturers often implement limitations in software. The former restrictions applied for altitudes higher than 60 000 ft (18.3km) and when traveling faster than 1000 kn (514 m/s). This is why some GPS receivers cease providing valid data, when both of the limits are exceeded. However, some devices

already stop working, when just one of the two conditions is fulfilled and others only check one condition. There are manufacturers (e.g. Magellan Navigation, ADU5) offering the possibility to change the limits on request. There are also open-source systems available with the possibility to make changes to the firmware.

However, as part of the U.S. Export Control Regulations Initiative, GNSS receivers have been moved from the United States Munitions List to the Commerce Control List during the transition period from 2014 (effective date) to 2016 (transition end date) and the limits were changed. The licensing under Export Control Classification Number (ECCN) 7A105 on the Commerce Control List only affects “Receiving equipment for Global Navigation Satellite Systems [...] capable of providing navigation information at speeds in excess of 600 m/s” [76]. The same limitation is mentioned in the Missile Technology Control Regime (MTCR) Equipment, Software and Technology Annex [77]. This means, receivers used on high-altitude balloons are not affected. Nonetheless, currently sold receivers can still have the restrictions that comply with the former regulations. In this case, this causes some GPS devices to refuse to operate in high altitudes.

Table 5-4 shows usual characteristics of state-of-the-art GPS receivers. For position accuracy, two values are given, the first one being the accuracy for the standalone GPS-System, the second one indicating the enhanced accuracy using the methods discussed above (DGPS, RTK)

Table 5-4: GPS sensors currently on the market.

Product Name	Company	Country	Attitude Accuracy (RMS, 1 m Antenna Separation) [°]	Positioning Accuracy (RMS) [m]	Update Rate [Hz]	Power Consumption [W]	Environmental Endurance Range, e.g. Temperature [°C]	Weight [kg]	Limitations
AsteRx-U	Septentrio	Belgium	0.1 (Yaw) 0.2 (Pitch/Roll)	2- 0.1 (RTK)	20	7	-30 – 65	1.5	N/A
GPS 18x	Garmin	Switzerland	N/A	15- 3 (WAAS) (2 sigma)	5	0.5	-30 – 80	0.1	514 m/s speed
Vector H321	Hemisphere GNSS	USA	0.1 (Yaw) 1 (Pitch/Roll) (2 sigma)	2.5- 0.02 (RTK) (2 sigma)	10-20	4.3-4.7	-40 – 85	0.1	18.3 km altitude or 514 m/s speed
Geo-PNT	Spectracom	USA	0.5 (Yaw) 0.2 (Pitch/Roll)	2.5- 0.1 (RTK)	100-125	9-13	-40 – 65	0.75	10.7 km altitude
Piksi (open source)	Swift Navigation	USA	N/A	5- 0.06 (RTK)	10	0.5	-40 – 85	0.032 (without antenna)	18.3 km altitude and 514 m/s speed, Modifiable open source firmware
ADU5	Magellan Navigation	USA	0.4 (Yaw) 0.8 (Pitch/Roll) (2 sigma)	5- 0.9 (DGPS) (2 sigma)	5	6	Receiver: -20 – 55 Antenna: -40 – 65	1.93	18.3 km altitude or 514 m/s speed (Higher altitudes and speeds available)
NetR9	Trimble	USA	N/A	5- 0.015 (RTK)	10-50	3.8	-40 – 65	1.75	N/A

5.3.3 Gyroscope Sensors

Gyroscope Sensors are used for precise pointing and stabilization systems and a large range of further applications such as consumer electronics, automobile systems or military applications. Consequently, a wide range of gyroscope devices with diverse performance characteristics and different measurement principles exist.

Figure 5-4: Fizoptika fiber optic gyroscope VG910, [78].

It is common practice to mount three gyroscopes orthogonally to each other close to the center of rotation to gain attitude information of the rigid body of a telescope, satellite or other inertial stabilized system. As the gyroscopes measure rates, the predicted attitude usually contains a so-called gyro-drift, which degrades the accuracy over time. That is one of the key characteristics to watch out for when choosing the sensor.

The mostly used gyro technologies are fiber optic gyros (FOG), as used in e.g. SOFIA, and micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS)-based gyros. Fiber optic gyros compare the phase of two laser beams, which travel into opposite directions through a coil of fiber optic cable. Rotation will cause a change in the phase difference, which is translated into the rotation rate [79]. MEMS gyros detect rotation rates by changes in the frequency of an oscillating mass due to the inertial force. Fiber optic gyros usually have low angular random walk, low drift and show high resistance against temperature changes, shock and vibration. Micro-electro-mechanical systems are usually smaller in size and weight and have a lower price. However, they lack in accuracy compared to FOGs.

The performance is characterized by different errors, which have to be considered when choosing a suitable device:

The rate bias is the remaining output signal deviation, when the gyro is at rest. This zero offset depends on temperature and can be compensated by a temperature dependent bias model, which is generated during calibration. However, after removing the bias, a low-frequency fluctuation will still be present in the output signal, the so-called bias instability, a quantity given in units of degree per hour. A second very important quantity is the angular random walk, a noise term with a white noise spectrum on the gyroscope rate output. When the rate signal is integrated to yield the measured angle, the noise becomes a random walk in angle, which is typified by a small varying drift with increasing variance over time [79].

Standard FOGs feature output rates of about 500 Hz to 2000 Hz, enabling a broad bandwidth. However, due to the drift increasing with time, standalone gyroscope usage in absence of any other reference is not practicable. Absolute attitude information by

other sensors is required for drift compensation. State-of-the-art systems combine gyro sensors with high output rates with slowly updating sensors, such as star trackers, which provide precise absolute attitude information.

Table 5-5 gives an overview of fiber optic gyroscope manufacturers and characteristics of different commercially available sensors.

Table 5-5: Gyroscope sensor selection.

Product Name	FOG2-80	Fiber Optic Gyro	VG910	FOG 24	GG1320AN	DSP-1760	EMP 1.2K
Company	NEDAERO	Saab	Fizoptica	Al cielo	Honeywell Aerospace	KVH	EMCORE
Country	Netherlands	Sweden	Russia	Israel	USA	USA	USA
Axes	1	1	1	1	1	1 – 3	1
Angular Random Walk [$^{\circ}/\sqrt{h}$]		0.05	0.015	0.0002	0.0035	0.012	0.002
Bias instability (const. Temp) [$^{\circ}/hr$]	0.2	1	1	0.001	0.0035	0.1	0.03
Scale Factor Non-Linearity [ppm]	N/A	10-30	0.2	2	5	50	25
Dynamic Range [$^{\circ}/s$]	+/- 300	+/- 150	+/- 250	+/- 30	+/- 900	+/- 490	+/- 343
Pricing [\$]	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	38.000
Power Consumption [W]	N/A	N/A	1.5	N/A	1.6	6-8	N/A
Mass [kg]	0.12		0.12		0.5	0.5-0.6	
Max. Sample Frequency [Hz]	N/A	N/A	1200	N/A	5000	1000	N/A
Resolution [arcsec/s]	N/A	N/A	0.119	N/A	1.113	Single Precision Floating Point (IEEE-754)	0.027
Environmental Endurance Range, e.g. Temperature [$^{\circ}C$]	-40 – 70	N/A	-40 – 75	“suitable for space applications”	-54 – 85	-40 – 75	N/A

5.3.4 Rotary Encoders

Rotary encoders can be used to precisely determine relative attitude between the telescope and the gondola. Measurement usually involves a disc containing markers and magnetic or optical sensors. Rotation of a shaft connected to the disc will shift the code, making the movement measurable. Two measurement principles can be distinguished: Incremental rotary encoders detect incremental changes of angular position. For absolute angular data, the changes have to be summed up.

Figure 5-5: ACURO AC58 rotary encoder [80].

After startup or after a power-loss, the initial angle has to be determined by a reference run. Absolute rotary encoders measure absolute angles and do not require reference runs after startup or after a power failure and therefore provide a higher degree of robustness. Rotary encoders cannot determine deflections of the whole gondola along the suspension rope, so supplementary sensors have to be used for precise pointing. Table 5-6 lists a selection of 7 manufacturers and shows typical characteristics of fine-precision encoders.

Table 5-6: Rotary encoders and manufacturers.

Manufacturer	Country	Product Name	Resolution [bit]	Accuracy [arcsec]	Weight [kg]	Temperature Range [°C]
Kuebler	Germany	Sendix 5873	21	N/A	0.35	-40 – 90
Pepperl+Fuchs	Germany	AHS58-H	16	N/A	0.3	-40 – 85
Hengstler	Germany	AC 58	22	35	0.42	-40 – 100
Baumer Group	Switzerland	HMG10	20	N/A	1.6	-40 – 85
Rockwell Automation	USA	Bulletin 845G	15	40	0.91	0 – 85
BEI Sensors	USA	CHM5	16	N/A	0.3	-20 – 90
Broadcom Limited	USA	AS38-H39E	23	80	N/A	-20 – 105

5.3.5 Star Tracker

Star trackers are systems consisting of one or more cameras and a computer or embedded controller that interprets images of the sky and compares observed star patterns with known maps of the star field in order to obtain precise attitude information.

Figure 5-6: Star Tracker 5000 sensor [81].

Commercially available products feature precision up to the sub-arcsecond range. However, due to a high computational effort, update rates are usually too slow (0.5-30Hz, see Table 5-7) for a suitable bandwidth of pointing control systems. Therefore, it is common practice to combine star tracker systems with fast-updating sensors, e.g. gyros. Star trackers usually operate in two modes. When no initial attitude information is available (this state is sometimes referred to as “Lost-In-Space”), the computer carries out a search algorithm in an onboard database of star-patterns. This operation usually requires a high computation time. When approximate attitude information exists, e.g. from previous measurements, computation time can be significantly reduced, as the star tracker only has to track previously identified stars at known positions [47]. For determining star positions on the image, different centroid algorithms exist. Taking into account the intensity distribution, subpixel accuracy can be achieved.

Star tracker precision is limited by various errors [47]:

Line of Sight uncertainty is caused by mechanical excursions which cannot be calibrated. These excursions can be caused by thermal effects, for example.

A combination of all error sources determines the angular resolution of the attitude. Calibration errors, condition of the hardware and algorithmic approximations contribute to the overall error. Over the camera’s lifetime, errors could increase, i.e. when the sensor array is subjected to radiation, the homogeneity of the pixel response will deteriorate as sensitivity changes.

The deployment of star trackers on high-altitude balloons during daylight is discussed by Truesdale et al. [82]. They show that during daytime operation, background noise heavily increases, making attitude determination challenging or even prevent useful results. Therefore, other sensors such as sun sensors are required in such a case.

An assortment of star tracker manufacturers and exemplary products is summarized in Table 5-7.

In addition to these commercially available, there are developments in the CubeSat sector to build low-cost star tracker. Prof. W.H. Steyn and Alex Erlank at the University of Stellenbosch at the Electronic Systems Laboratory presented such a system in [83]. They

use a CMOS Camera and developed an algorithm for tracking and for lost-in-space recovery. The simulated resolution is 0.006° .

Table 5-7: Selection of commercially available star trackers.

Product	ST5000	CT-602	AST-301	Visible band Star Tracker	Hydra	Astro 10	A-STR/AA-STR
Company	UW-SAL	Ball Aerospace	Lockheed Martin	OPC	Sodern	Jena Optronik	Leonardo
Country	USA	USA	USA	USA	France	Germany	Italy
Update Rate [Hz]	10	10	N/A	2	30	8	4-10
Accuracy [arcsec]	0.5	5	0.16	1.44 (SNR limit)	4 (3 σ)	1.5 (1 σ)	8-10 (3 σ)
Mass [kg]	4	5.4	N/A	0.2	1.9	3	2.6-3.5
Power Consumption [W]	12	8	N/A	2	10	5-10	5-14
Environmental Endurance Range, e.g. Temperature [°C]	Qualified for space	Qualified for space	Qualified for space	-30 – 55 Qualified for space	-30 – 60 Qualified for space	-30 – 60 Qualified for space	-30 – 60 Ambient or vacuum Qualified for space

5.3.6 Sun Sensors

Sun sensors determine the sun's position relative to the sensor using a specifically shaped entrance window through which sunlight falls on an array of photosensitive detectors. Different angles of incidence result in different light distributions on the sensor array.

Figure 5-7: Sun sensor ISS-D5 [84].

Sun sensors can provide precise measurements of arcsec-level resolution [69].

Table 5-8 provides a representative list of state-of-the-art sun sensors:

Table 5-8: Sun sensors and manufacturers.

Company	Country	Product Name	Accuracy [°]	Range [°]	Axes	Environmental Endurance Range, e.g. Temperature [°C]
Solar MEMS	Spain	ISS-D5	0.1 (3 σ)	10	2	-40 – 85
Bradford	Netherlands	Fine Sun Sensor	0.3 (3 σ)	128	2	-50 – 85
Crystal Space	Estonia	S1U	0.5	45	2	Qualified for space
Surrey Satellite Technology	UK	Two-Axis DMC Sun Sensor	1 (2 σ)	50	2	-30 – 60
Adcole Corporation	USA	Fine Sun Sensor	0.01	100	1	Qualified for space
Lens R&D ^{vv}	Netherlands	BiSon64-B	0.5 (3 σ)	116	2	Qualified for space

5.3.7 Magnetometers

Magnetometers detect changes in the direction of the Earth’s magnetic field with respect to the sensors. Using the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration World Magnetic Model, azimuth and elevation can be estimated. However, for balloon experiments like BLASTPol and Spider, the magnetometer turned out to be less useful than other sensors due to large errors of > 5 deg [28].

5.4 ACTUATORS

This section gives a short introduction about suitable actuator types on balloons. Current and previously flown balloon-borne observatories usually consist of a gimbal-mechanism that allows the science instrument to be freely turned around two axes. The axis along the balloon’s suspension line is referred to as the azimuth axis, the term elevation is used to refer to motion around the axis parallel to the earth’s surface and perpendicular to the telescopes line of sight. Some observatories (HALO, superBIT) also allow for a roll motion around the science instrument’s line of sight.

Most balloon-borne observatories use a reaction wheel as a primary component for controlling the azimuthal angle. A motor attached to the reaction wheel can apply a momentum to the wheel resulting in a counter-momentum due to Newton’s third law, which acts on the gondola. However, rotational speed of the reaction wheel is limited by friction and motor characteristics, thus an additional motor is required for dumping

^{vv} Low accuracy (~0.5 deg), low cost option; space qualified version around 4 to 5 kEUR (see catalogue at <https://lens-rnd.com/download/product-and-price-catalogue-2017/>); accuracy increases with decreasing FOV.

excess angular momentum to the balloon. The reaction wheel should ideally have a large momentum of inertia but still be lightweight in order to minimize additional weight to the whole payload. A large angular momentum results from a large diameter and from concentrating the mass close to the outer radius.

It is common practice to integrate the additional azimuth motor into the pivot, which yields the azimuthal angle degree of freedom and connects the gondola to the balloon tether. This motor alone without the reaction wheel cannot provide the same control behaviour as the combined system, because a rapid control response would be disturbed by the torsional flexibility of the suspension line between [1].

For elevation control, either a linear or a rotary actuator that controls the telescope's elevation angle with respect to the outer gimbal frame or gondola can be a suitable choice. Aside from a gimbal mount, an actuated mirror can be used for elevation pointing. Rotary actuators are mounted close to the suspension, whereas linear actuators can make use of a large lever arm when mounted further away.

Pointing control systems usually require motors which provide high torque at low speeds. Static friction should be as small as possible, as the motors will often reverse direction and carry out only small motions. In order to completely get rid of static friction, the WASP-System [85] uses an additional small motor for each motor hub, to keep the central shaft constantly rotated.

Electric motors can be installed as direct drive motors or with additional reductions such as a gearbox. While direct drive motors are usually larger for generating high torque at very low speeds, a gearbox might increase friction, reduce drive stiffness and introduce backlash. This means, direct drive motors achieve higher accuracies and show a better dynamic performance. Therefore, a direct drive motor is considered to be more suitable for pointing control applications. Furthermore, the motor should allow for direct-current input, as only a dc-power supply (batteries and solar panels, see chapter 7) will be available during the mission.

Figure 5-8: Tecnoion torque motor [86].

Existing balloon-borne pointing systems use motors with typically ~10-30 Nm, for example, the BLAST experiment uses torque motors with a peak torque of 13.6 Nm [29].

For comparison of the different actuators, the following two quantities are important:

- 1) The motor constant K_m is a measure of efficiency, showing the relationship between produced torque and power losses. Efficiency increases with high K_m values.
- 2) The torque sensitivity K_t , which is the ratio between torque and current.

As most manufacturers offer a wide range of motors in order to fit the specific application, only a short representative list of torque motors that operate with a peak torque of about 30 Nm is presented here.

Table 5-9 lists manufacturers of diverse dc direct drive brushless torque motors:

Table 5-9: DC torque motors and manufacturers.

Manufacturer	Country	Product (Exemplary)	K_m [Nm W ⁻²]	K_t [Nm A ⁻¹]	Weight [kg]	Peak Torque [Nm]
Etel	Switzerland	TMB+0175	N/A	N/A	N/A	34.2
Tecnotion	Netherlands	QTR-A-105-60	0.63	2.86	1.909	28.4
Georgii Kobold	Germany	KTY 6284.04 F-Rx/230	0.95	6.53		32
Akribis Systems	USA	ATR 152-138	1.86	5.15	8.5	53.5
Aerotech	USA	S-130-102A	0.71	2.48	7	30.75
Kollmorgen	USA	QT-11302	2.14		4.0	29.8
Moog	USA	DB-4000	0.91	1.16	6.17	35.0

Electric power consumption depends on the provided mechanical power and electrical power losses within the motor. It does not only depend on the motor's characteristics but also on the control algorithm and environmental disturbances, which dictate the motor's workload. This should be considered in the future [design](#)^[KS1].

6 COMMUNICATION AND REMOTE CONTROL

6.1 COMMUNICATION SYSTEMS AND FREQUENCIES FOR DIFFERENT APPLICATIONS

Two principal types of communication are implemented on balloon flights: communication with the balloon flight service system itself and communication with the payload. Each of them poses specific requirements: the flight service system communication only requires moderate data rates, but almost permanent connectivity in order to allow piloting of the balloon or flight abort commands; the payload communication on the other hand requires higher downlink data rates if scientific data is to be downlinked during the flight, but not necessarily permanent connectivity. Given these different requirements, and the particular safety concept applied, flight service communication and payload communication may use the same or separate communication systems.

6.1.1 Line-of-Sight Communication

Frequency bands used for line-of-sight communication are typically high frequency (HF), ultra high frequency (UHF), L-Band, or S-Band. Each of them will be shortly described in the following, including their present and past application for ballooning.

HF

- Frequency range: 3 to 30 MHz
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- Communication systems in the high frequency range are currently under consideration by CNES for the NOSYCA (New Operational SYstem for the Control of Aerostats) balloon operation system. [87]

UHF

- Frequency range: 0.3 to 1 GHz (for EBASS: 449.95 MHz uplink, 402.2 MHz downlink [17], at CSBF: 429.5 MHz [88])
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- UHF communication systems were used by CNES for a long time to control zero pressure balloons (ZPBs). While they were replaced by an L-Band link on the ETNA 2 (Equipment of TM/TC for Nacelle, starting in 1999) system and an S-Band link on the NOSYCA system (flight proven in 2013) [89], they remained under consideration for the NOSYCA systems [87].
- UHF communication is also used by the NASA Columbia Scientific Ballooning Facility (CSBF) for service communication with ZPBs which are typically equipped with two UHF antennas below the main gondola for this purpose. [90]
- UHF communication was also used by the Italian Space Agency ASI on their ballooning base in Trapani Milo. The base was equipped with a stationary and a mobile ground station for the UHF link. [91]
- SSC uses UHF communication on their Estringe Balloon Service System (EBASS), primarily for service TC and TM. The bandwidth of the implemented system is nominally 38.4 kbit/s for both TC and TM, using the frequency at 449.95 MHz for

uplink and 402.2 MHz for downlink. More details on the ground station and the flight equipment are provided in section 6.3. [17]

L-Band:

- Frequency range: around 1500 MHz (1444.5 MHz to 1525.5 MHz at CSBF [88])
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- L-Band communication was used by the ETNA and ETNA 2 systems of CNES for service and payload communication [24, 89]. Using Quaternary Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) modulation in combination with Viterbi error correction coding and data scrambling, the ETNA 2 system could provide between 250 kbit/s and 2 Mbit/s downlink capacity and 115 kbit/s uplink capacity [89]. The ETNA and ETNA 2 communication architectures were based on TCP/IP environments. It was replaced by S-Band communication in the NOSYCA system.
- The Italian Space Agency ASI used an L-Band communication system provided by the French company ELTA for service and payload communication. The L-Band link could be complemented by an Iridium module (IRIASI) to provide over-the-horizon TM/TC for the service systems, particularly for long duration balloon flights. [92]
- L-Band communication is also used by CSBF for service and payload communication. For this purpose, typically 2 L-Band antennas are installed on the bottom of the main gondola for service communication, along with one separate antenna for payload communication. [90]

S-Band:

- Frequency range: 2405 – 2496 MHz^{ww} / 2378.5 – 2387.5 MHz^{xx}
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- S-Band communication is used by CNES in their latest NOSYCA balloon operation system for service and payload communication with ZPBs. Like in the ETNA 2 system, the communication architecture is based on TCP/IP. It provides 2 Mbit/s downlink capacity and 100 kbit/s uplink capacity. The NOSYCA S-Band transceiver uses QPSK modulation and Viterbi error correction coding. In combination with the NOSYCA on-board router, Reed-Solomon error correction coding can be used for both telemetry (TM) and telecommand (TC). [93]
- S-Band communication is also used on the Swedish Space Corporation's (SSC) E-Link system for payload communication, providing a nominal duplex capacity of 2 Mbit/s. The E-Link system also offers TCP/IP interfaces. [17]
- S-Band communication was also used by ASI on their ballooning base in Trapani Milo. The base was equipped with a stationary and a mobile ground station for the S-Band link. [91]

^{ww} For SSC E-Link [17]

^{xx} At CSBF [88]

6.1.2 Over-the-Horizon Communication

Iridium:

Iridium refers to a range of services provided by the U.S.-based company Iridium Communications Inc., using their constellation of low-Earth orbit communication satellites. The current constellation consists of 66 active satellites, providing permanent global coverage. Iridium is currently launching a new generation of satellites, the Iridium NEXT constellation, which will offer improved services over the current constellation. The Iridium NEXT constellation is expected to be completed in mid-2018 [94].

Usage prices for Iridium services are provided in Annex I. Commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) equipment is available for all Iridium services, but not necessarily equipment qualified for or tested by use in the stratosphere.

- Frequency range: 1616-1626.5 MHz
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- Coverage: worldwide, continuous coverage
- Services:
 - *Iridium Short Burst Data (SBD)*. The SBD service provides a low-latency link for short messages, optimized for 340-character uplink messages and 270-character downlink messages [95]. SBD data modems have low mass, small form factors, and a low power consumption. Ground-based access to SBD services can be established via internet, the usual latency is less than one minute. The service is thus well suited for backup service TM/TC, recovery beacon messages, or also downlink of small amounts of data. SBD is used by CNES on the NOSYCA system for recovery location messages [87] and by the CSBF for uplink of commands and downlink of science packages [90].
 - *Iridium Dial-Up Data Service/Direct Internet Service/Point-to-Point Protocol/RUDICS^{yy}* are all circuit-switched data services that allow bi-directional, continuous real-time data transfer of up to 2.4 kbit/s per channel. The individual services differ in convenience for stratospheric balloon applications and several of them have been used in the past, which is why each of them shall be introduced shortly.

Dial-Up Data Service offers connectivity on the ground-application side via the Public Switched Telephone Network, i.e. via analog modems. The connection can be initiate from both the ground application and the remote unit, but the ground-access via an analog connection makes it inconvenient. Iridium Dial-Up Data Service was used and continues to be available for command uplink and science data downlink for CSBF flights [90] and was used by ASI on the IRIASI system [96]. This service is likely also the one used by CNES' NOSYCA system for service and payload TM and TC in case for long duration flights [97]. The STRADIUM TM/TC system developed in Italy likely also uses the Dial-Up Data Service (even though it might also be compatible with RUDICS). A special feature of the STRADIUM system was that it provided the option of using two Iridium channels for service TM/TC and up to twelve channels for payload

^{yy} All information from [130], unless otherwise noted.

TM/TC, providing bandwidths of up to 4.8 kbit/s for service communication and up to 14.4 kbit/s for payload communication [98].

Direct Internet Service offers direct connection to the internet on the ground-based side via channeling of the data through an Iridium internet server. It requires a Windows operating system on the remote unit side, however, and the remote unit must initiate any session. It is thus less suitable for balloon operations.

Point-to-Point Protocol is similar to “Direct Internet”, but compatible with any operating system on the remote unit client side. The remote unit must still initiate any session, however, making it less suitable for balloon operations.

Iridium Router based Unrestricted Digital Interworking Connectivity Solution (RUDICS) provides an end-to-end IP connection via the circuit-switched data service, making interfacing on both sides convenient. No restrictions on the remote unit operating system exist, and connections can be initiated both from the remote/flight unit and the ground unit. RUDICS has been used by SSC on the PoGOLite flight [99].

- *Iridium Pilot/OpenPort*. Iridium Pilot is a product to provide broadband IP-based data service and phone connections using the Iridium OpenPort broadband service. It is tailored towards maritime users, but is also frequently used for stratospheric balloons. Iridium Pilot hardware is commercially available, offering up to 134 kbit/s bidirectional throughput^{zz}. Required hardware consists of an electronically steered antenna and the transceiver and modem in the “Below Deck Unit” (BDU). The hardware is considerably heavier than that for Iridium SBD, but provides much higher data rates and a connection of the on-board equipment to the internet, which makes for convenient interfacing. Iridium Pilot equipment is used by the CSBF [90].

INMARSAT

The British company Inmarsat plc provides satellite communication services from geostationary satellites. The most interesting services, the Broadband Global Area Network (BGAN) and FleetBroadband (FB), are provided by the three Inmarsat-4 satellites, which offer the coverage shown in Figure 6-1 (other Inmarsat services are provided through the Inmarsat-3 or Inmarsat-5 geostationary satellites offering very similar coverage, all excluding the polar regions).

^{zz} The CSBF quotes the typical throughput as ca. 75 kbit/s [90].

Figure 6-1: Coverage of Inmarsat BGAN and FleetBroadband services [100].

Inmarsat offers both broadband services (most interestingly for balloons BGAN and FleetBroadband) and low speed data services (BGAN ISATPHONE), which will be shortly introduced in the following. Pricing information for these services is provided in Annex III and Annex IV. The use of BGAN has been considered by CNES [89] and the CSBF [90], the use of the low speed BGAN ISATPHONE by CNES [89]. While the NOSYCA system was prepared to support Inmarsat communication connectivity [97], there seem to be RF compatibility issues between the Inmarsat and the Iridium equipment in NOSYCA flight models, so that Inmarsat communication is not used [87]. Satellite-to-ground communication uses the L-Band, just as Iridium. A large range of commercial-off-the-shelf equipment is available for all Inmarsat services, but not necessarily equipment qualified for use in the stratosphere.

- Frequency range: Rx: 1525.0 - 1559.0 MHz, Tx: 1626.5 - 1660.5 MHz
- Typical type of connection: bi-directional
- Coverage: see Figure 6-1, continuous
- Services:
 - *INMARSAT Broadband Global Area Network (BGAN)* offers broadband data via a TCP/IP environment at very high data rates up to 432 kbit/s [89]. The use of BGAN for stratospheric balloons was studied by CNES [89] and the CSBF [90]. The main disadvantages over Iridium are the long distance to the geostationary satellites, which require either high transmit power or a preferably steerable high gain antenna on the balloon, and the lack of coverage above ca. 80 deg northern and southern latitude.
 - *INMARSAT FleetBroadband* is technically the same service as BGAN, but marketed and sold in conjunction with maritime stabilized antennas and adapted equipment (even though there are also auto-pointing antennas for classical BGAN). Available pricing plans very slightly compared to those for BGAN.
 - *INMARSAT IsatPhone* is a satellite phone service, including corresponding hardware, offered by Inmarsat that also can be used for data transfer. It uses the same satellite fleet as BGAN and can provide data rates of 2.4 kbit/s, making it particularly suitable for service TM/TC [89]. While IsatPhone

COTS equipment is available, as of 2011, there was no customized equipment for stratospheric conditions yet [89].

Skywave propagation^{aaa}

Skywave propagation is a technique to communicate with remote equipment beyond the line of sight/local horizon making use of the propagation/reflection of low frequency waves in the ionosphere. Generally usable frequencies are between 3.5 and 30 MHz, the exact frequencies to be used depend upon the location of the transmitter and receiver, the current solar radiation, the time of day at transmission, and other factors. Skywave propagation is frequently used by radio amateurs and was used by CNES for telemetry downlink from Montgolfier Infrarouge balloons between 1976 and 1996 using the CHACAL communication system. The system was operated using three ground stations, each ca. 15,000 km apart and operated at a bandwidth of 100 bit/s. Obvious shortcomings were the lack of a telecommand channel and the low bandwidth. CNES initiated a study in 2007 on “Numerical Short Wave” to investigate the possibility of using skywave propagation with both TM and TC capability and with new transceivers. Little information is available on these efforts, however.

TDRSS^{bbb}

The Tracking and Data Relay Satellite System (TDRSS) is a network of geostationary communication satellites managed and operated by NASA. Its original purpose was to provide low Earth orbiting satellites and spacecraft with more continuous connectivity and higher communication data rates. It is being used for near continuous communication with the International Space Station and the Hubble Space Telescope, for example. The TDRSS satellites provide S-Band, Ka-Band, and Ku-Band links (due to the available data rate and the power requirements of higher frequency transmitters (Ka and Ku), the author assumes that the S-Band capability is used for balloon communication). The CSBF uses TDRSS for telemetry downlink, either with an omnidirectional antenna or a steered high-gain antenna on the balloon. With an omnidirectional antenna, a data rate of 6 to 10 kbit/s can be reached, with a steered high-gain antenna 93 kbit/s. Frequencies used for TDRSS communication are 2106.5 MHz for uplink and 2287.5 MHz for downlink [88].

NASA is currently conducting further test flights with the Low Cost TDRSS Transceiver (LCT2), which promises available data rates of 300 to 500 kbit/s through an S-Band TDRSS connection when using a high-gain antenna. A test flight at 150 kbit/s was conducted in 2015, further tests at higher rates were planned for 2016.

Availability of the TDRSS system, and conditions thereof, to non-U.S.-government customers would need to be investigated.

6.2 ONBOARD COMPUTING AND DATA STORAGE

In regards to onboard computing and data storage, again a distinction needs to be made between flight service equipment and payload equipment. Several standardized systems exist for the former and some basic systems exist for the latter, the baseline assumption

^{aaa} See [89] unless otherwise mentioned.

^{bbb} See [90], unless otherwise mentioned.

seems to be, however, that experiments provide their own payload computer and data acquisition/data storage management.

A selection of the existing on-board computing / balloon operation systems will be presented in the follow. The listing does not claim to be complete or to favor the mentioned companies and institutions, but to provide a first overview. Data storage and payload computing equipment will be discussed in more detail in the ORISON Feasibility Report.

NOSYCA (CNES)^{ccc}

CNES started to develop NOSYCA as a new reliable and fail safe command control system for their stratospheric balloons in 2007 and eventually carried out first qualifying flights in 2013. The TM/TC capabilities of NOSYCA were already mentioned in chapter 6.1.

NOSYCA is a modular system for flight trains with nominally three different gondolas. It includes three different OBCs and one payload interface module, distributed among the gondolas as follows:

- The *Envelope Gondola* is attached to the balloon envelope itself and fulfills basic functions related to flight safety and localization of the envelope. It contains one OBC with an Iridium SBD communication interface to the ground station, GPS, safety equipment, and an Argos beacon.
- The *Operational Gondola* is located below the parachute on the main part of the flight train. It contains two OBCs: one OBC for nominal operations, using an S-Band modem for balloon-to-ground communication; and one redundant OBC for backup, using an Iridium modem for balloon-to-ground communication. The operational gondola also usually carries the ballast reservoir module.
- The *Payload Gondola*, located below the Operational Gondola and carrying the payload. It also carries a SIREN interface module to the Operational Gondola, providing communication routing from the Operational Gondola to the Payload Gondola and vice versa. The communication link between the Operational Gondola and SIREN is nominally a Wi-Fi link, but can optionally also be replaced by a cable-based RS485 serial connection (necessary if over-the-horizon communication for the payload is required).

The OBCs use a distributed architecture and are built on stackable pluggable boards, using a PCI-bus for communication among each other. While the boards and OBCs are custom, the Wi-Fi connection uses consumer products that were adapted to the balloon environment.

The SIREN interface provides the following connections for the payload:

- Ethernet
- Up to 8 RS232 asynchronous full duplex serial channels
- One RS422 serial synchronous TM data link for high speed science data
- Network Time Protocol

^{ccc} See [97], unless otherwise mentioned

-
- Pulse Per Second output
 - On/off command lines.

Each SIREN on-board interface adapter is tied to a ground-based SIREN SOL unit that serves as the ground-based interface to the payload.

While the OBCs provide storage for TM, TC, and on-board events, they do not seem to provide storage for payload data. For short duration flights, each OBC is furthermore equipped with a dedicated battery sized according to the expected flight time.

NOSYCA hardware elements are available from ELTA.

E-Link / EBASS (SSC/DLR)^{ddd}

The Esrange Balloon Service System (EBASS) and the E-Link system are standard systems used for SSC balloon flights, e.g. for the BEXUS campaigns. Thereby, EBASS is used mainly for flight and balloon control, whereas E-Link is used as an interface for payload communication.

EBASS therefore mainly serves for: altitude control, flight termination, localization, and housekeeping. It is also equipped with three serial connections for payload control and data reception, however, and can provide payload communication with limited bandwidth.

E-Link is a dedicated communication interface for payload data, providing payload connectivity through 2 Ethernet interfaces and 3 asynchronous RS232/RS422 serial channels.

Both E-Link and EBASS run on dedicated batteries. Neither of them provides data storage for payload data.

Details on the EBASS and E-Link units can also be found in section 6.4.

Universal Data Handling System (SSC)^{eee}

The Universal Data Handling System is the result of a study conducted at SSC in 2012 on the feasibility of a common Data Handling System for sounding rockets and balloons. The system is modular and based on individually distributable boards, making it flexible both in terms of accommodation on the vehicle as well as for different mission scenarios. It includes several interesting features:

- Separate boards with equal form factor for individual functions;
- Interface among service boards and to science experiments via CAN bus (the CAN bus is more robust compared to RS422/RS485 and is suitable for a multimaster environment, rather than Master/Slave);
- Asynchronous RS422/RS485 serial interface for backward compatibility;
- Common 28 V power bus for all boards (typical power consumption per board: 2-4 W, TM/TC board: 7 W).

Individual boards that were realized in 2015 were:

- Power Control and Distribution Board, connecting to an 8-cell Li-Ion battery, providing 0.2 kWh capacity;

^{ddd} See [17] unless otherwise mentioned

^{eee} See [131] unless otherwise mentioned

-
- Telemetry and Telecommand Board;
 - Application-specific Sensor and Actuator Boards for the following functions: temperature sensors interface, heater interface, analogue output/input interface, pulse-width modulated output interface.

Boards that were under consideration in 2015 are particularly a high capacity power module, which would allow to connect several modules managing a battery capacity of 1.6 kWh each, and a solar panel control board.

It is not known to the author whether the Universal Data Handling System has flown on a balloon to date.

Support Instrumentation Package (CSBF)^{fff}

For long duration balloon flights (i.e. ca. 5 to 15 days), the CSBF flies a Support Instrumentation Package (SIP) that serves as the interface to the scientific payload. In contrast to the other abovementioned systems, the SIP includes hard drives that can be used to store science data. Furthermore, it serves as the interface to the TDRSS and Iridium satellite communication connections, as well as to the L-Band or S-Band line-of-sight connections, if necessary. The between payload computer and SIP is realized via an RS232 serial connection and a custom protocol.

For scientists with basic requirements who do not want to provide their own payload computer, the CSBF also offers the option to add a “Science Stack”, providing 32 analogue channels for return telemetry, 16 digital channels for return telemetry, 28 open-collector command outputs, 1 times open-collector command output, and a 5 V reference.

Details on the SIP can also be found in section 6.4

Payload Computer^{ggg}

One known implementation of a payload computer is that of the E and B Experiment (EBEX) balloon missions. EBEX used ruggedized single board COTS computers (AMPRO computers from ADLINK Technology, Inc.) in combination with solid state disks which were operated at ambient pressure. Two redundant computers were used, with a steady state power consumption of 19.5 W each.

^{fff} See [88], unless otherwise mentioned

^{ggg} See [27], unless otherwise mentioned

6.3 MARKET OFFER OF COMPONENTS

Table 6-1: Available transceivers and antennas.

Type	System name	Band	Manufacturer	TC data rate [kbit/s]	TM data rate [Mbit/s]	Transmitter output	Receiver sensitivity	Mass [kg]	Operational Voltage [VDC]	Power consumption		Operating Temp. Range		Item Cost [USD]	Additional information	Used on/by	Source
										Idle [W]	Operational [W]	Min [°C]	Max [°C]				
Transceiver	ETNA 2 /IRILASI	L-Band	ELTA (France)	115	0.25 – 2	24 dBm (250 mW output) to 30 dBm (1W output)	-115 dB @ 57 kbps	0.72	11 – 15		8 max.	-40	50		QPSK modulation, Viterbi coding, TCP/IP based	CNES	[101]
Iridium Transceiver	IRIASI	L-Band	ELTA (France)	2.4	0.0024			2.8 ^{hhh}	7.5 – 14		7.5 avg.	-40	60			ASI	[96]
Transceiver	NOSYCA	S-Band	ELTA (France)	100	2	-10 dBm to 29 dBm	-114 dBm for a BER of 10 ⁻⁶	0.69	9 – 16		12 (at +29 dBm)	-40	60		QPSK modulation, Viterbi coding, TCP/IP based, shock & vibr. qualified	CNES	[93]
On-Board Router	NOSYCA		ELTA (France)	100	2				10 – 16.8		4	-40	70		Reed-Solomon coding for TM & TC, RS232 link to OBC, optional WiFi, shock & vibr. qualified	CNES	[102]
Interface gondola to payload	NOSYCA (SIREN)		ELTA (France)					22							Autonomous for 72 h, completely flight qualified	CNES	[103]

^{hhh} Without battery

Iridium Control Telemetry Unit	MSITel	L-Band	LEN (Italy)	4.8 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.0048			8.6 ⁱⁱⁱ	9 – 40	0.25		-40	60			ASI	[104]
Iridium SBD Transceiver	Iridium 9603	L-Band	Iridium (U.S.)					0.011	5.0	0.2	0.8	-40	85	395 ^{kkk}			[105]
Iridium Antenna	SAF5350 -C ⁱⁱⁱ	L-Band	NAL Research Corporation (U.S.)	2.4	0.0024			0.146				-55	85		Certified up to 21 km altitude		[106]
Iridium Transceiver	A3LA-D	L-Band	NAL Research Corporation (U.S.)	2.4	0.0024			0.659	4.0 – 4.8	0.57	2.2	-20	60			ASI / STRADIUM	[107]
Iridium Transceiver	A3LA-RS	L-Band	NAL Research Corporation (U.S.)	2.4	0.0024			0.122	3.5 – 5.4	0.3	1.75	-30	70		Current model of the A3LA-D		[108]
Iridium Transceiver	A3LA-RG	L-Band	NAL Research Corporation (U.S.)	2.4	0.0024			0.201	4.0 – 5.4	0.875	2.1	-30	70		Similar to A3LA-RS, but includes GPS receiver		[109]
Iridium Transceiver	A3LA-X	L-Band	NAL Research Corporation (U.S.)	2.4	0.0024			0.34	4.0 – 32	1.5	4	-30	70		MIL-STD-810F certified	CSBF / BARREL	[110]

ⁱⁱⁱ Using two connected Iridium modems in “split mode” (2.4 kbit/s each). Up to 8 MSITel modules can be combined to provide up to 38.4 kbit/s duplex data rate.

^{jjj} MSITel opt 004, i.e. packaged in an IP66 box, including two Iridium modems and backup Li-Ion batteries.

^{kkk} Supplier: Outfitter Satellite Inc.

^{lll} Compatible with all listed NAL transceivers

Iridium Antenna	Pilot	L-Band	Iridium (U.S.)	134	0.134			12.7	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	-30	70	4,850 ^{mmm}		CSBF	[90]
Iridium Indoor Equipment	Pilot	L-Band	Iridium (U.S.)	134	0.134			1.35	11 – 32	18	31	0	50	658 ^{mmm}			[111]
TDRSS HGA								11.3								CSBF	[90]
Inmarsat FB Antenna	FB150	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM Maritime (DK)	150	0.15			3.9	10 – 32		Incl. in FB150 BDU power cons.	-25	55	5,200 ⁿⁿⁿ	TCP/IP based		[112]
Inmarsat FB Antenna	FB250	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM Maritime (DK)	284	0.284			4.2	10 – 32		Incl. in FB250 BDU power cons.	-25	55	9,100 ⁿⁿⁿ	TCP/IP based		[113]
Inmarsat FB Antenna	FB500	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM Maritime (DK)	432	0.432			23 ^{ooo}	10 – 32		Incl. in FB500 BDU power cons.	-25	55	15,500 ⁿⁿⁿ	TCP/IP based		[114]
Inmarsat FB BDU	FB150	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM Maritime (DK)	150	0.15			2	10 – 32		120 max ^{ppp}	-25	55	Incl. with antennas	TCP/IP based		[112]
Inmarsat FB BDU	FB250	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM	284	0.284			2.5	10 – 32		150 max ^{ppp}	-25	55	Incl. with antennas	TCP/IP based		[113]

^{mmm} Supplier: SatPhoneStore

ⁿⁿⁿ Supplier: MailASail

^{ooo} Data from [100]

^{ppp} Incl. antenna

			Maritime (DK)														
Inmarsat FB BDU	FB500	L-Band	Cobham SATCOM Maritime (DK)	432	0.432			2.5 ⁹⁹⁹	10 – 32		150 max ^{PPP}	-25	55	Incl. with antennas	TCP/IP based		[114]
Inmarsat BGAN Antenna	9450-C11		Hughes (U.S.)	464	0.465			2				-25	55	6,995 ⁹⁹⁹	Tracking antenna		[115]
Inmarsat BGAN Transceiver	9450-C11		Hughes (U.S.)	464	0.465			2.3	12 or 24	32	65	-25	55	Incl. with antenna			[115]
Inmarsat BGAN Antenna	9450-C10		Hughes (U.S.)	492	0.492			5.5				-25	55	13,448 ⁹⁹⁹	Tracking antenna		[116]
Inmarsat BGAN Transceiver	9450-C10		Hughes (U.S.)	492	0.492			2.3	12 or 24	32	65	-25	55	Incl. with antenna			[116]
Inmarsat IsatPhone	IsatPhone Pro		Inmarsat (UK)	2.4	0.0024			0.279						795 ⁹⁹⁹	Standalone phone with internal Li battery		[117]

⁹⁹⁹ Supplier: Ground Control Systems Inc.

Table 6-2: Available ground station equipment.

Type	System Name	Band	Manufacturer	TC Data Rate [kbit/s]	TM Data Rate [Mbit/s]	Transmitter Output [EIRP]	Gain	Additional Information	Used by	Source
S-Band ground station	SCILA (NOSYCA)	S-Band	ELTA (France)	100	2	17.2 dBW	> 5 dB/°K (@5°)	QPSK modulation, Viterbi / Reed-Solomon encoding, Right Hand Circular Polarization	CNES	[97]
L-Band ground station	IRILASI	L-Band	ELTA (France)			10 W HPA		1.8 m parabolic antenna	CNES	[118]
Iridium ground station		L-Band	ELTA (France)					Equipped with Iridium modem	CNES	[119]
S-Band ground station	E-Link	S-Band		2000	2	Peak 10 W		Modulation: DSSS, max. range: 500 km ^{†††} 1.8 m parabolic antenna	SSC / BEXUS	[17]
UHF ground station	EBASS	UHF		38.4	0.0384	100 W	12 dBiC	Modulation: FM, range: 550 km ^{†††} , helical antenna, RHCP	SSC / BEXUS	[17]

^{†††} at 30 km float altitude and unobstructed line of sight

Table 6-3: Available integrated equipment.

Type	System Name	Band	TC Data Rate [kbit/s]	TM Data Rate [Mbit/s]	Transmitter Output	Mass [kg]	Operational Voltage [VDC]	Additional Information	Used on/by	Source
S-Band Communication Unit	E-Link	S-Band	2000	2	10 W peak	20 ^{sss}	20 – 38	DSSS modulation; Antenna: vertical polarized omnidirectional; max. range: 500 km ^{ttt}	SSC / BEXUS	[17]
Balloon Service System	EBASS	UHF	38.4	0.0384	100 W	25		Modulation: FM; max. range: 550 km ^{ttt} ; own battery supply; operational life time: 40 h with maximum battery configuration	SSC / BEXUS	[17]
Science Service System	Support Instrumentation Package	S-Band / L-Band				91 ^{ttt}			CSBF	[88]

^{sss} Nominally, including batteries for ca. 11 hours operation time, main unit, RF interface unit, and antenna

^{ttt} Including thermal shield

6.4 SAFETY SYSTEMS

Balloons larger than a certain size are required to carry additional communication equipment to comply with safety regulations if they pass flight corridors. The equipment carried for this purpose includes:

- Strobe lights which are required to be switched on while in flight corridors [87];
- Passive radar reflectors to enhance the radar cross section of the balloon;
- Air Traffic Control Radar Beacon System (ATCRB) transponders (often also just referred to as “ATC transponders”). These transponders return the balloon’s identification code and altitude information to the air traffic control Secondary Surveillance Radar upon request and enable the balloon’s integration into regular air traffic control operations. ATC transponders work at 1030 MHz for receiving and 1090 MHz for transmitting. [1] Typically, both the balloon envelope and the payload are separately equipped with ATC transponders and the transponders are active up to 23 km [17].

7 POWER SUPPLY

The following chapter is focusing on the power supply for all platform subsystems during flight. Primary batteries, and a combination of solar panels and secondary batteries have been considered.

7.1 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Batteries convert chemical into electrical energy. For primary batteries, this process is not reversible, i.e. they are not rechargeable. Secondary batteries are used to store energy provided by solar cells, as their conversion of chemical into electrical energy is reversible. They are important for conditioning solar powered systems, and save excess energy provided by the solar cells to supply it to the system when needed (e.g. peak loads, night time). Solar cells generate energy by the utilization of the photoelectric effect, and have to be oriented towards the sun for best efficiency (ideally perpendicular to the incoming solar radiation).

A literature review on former and currently active balloon-borne telescopes shows that both approaches have been used. Long-term missions like SPIDER [70], SuperBIT [30], BLAST [28] and BOOMERanG [120] with operation times of several days up to several months are using solar panels. Short-term missions like HEROES [121] with an operation time of merely 30-32 hours prefer primary batteries.

7.1.1 Batteries

The following two sections are describing the state-of-the-art of primary and secondary batteries.

7.1.2 Primary Batteries

This section describes the state-of-the-art of primary batteries according to [122], [123] and [124].

Table 7-1 [122] shows a comparison between different primary battery technologies and provides ratings from 1 (best) to 8 (poorest).

Lithium batteries show superior properties in comparison to the other cell technologies. The advantageous features of lithium batteries are a high voltage as well as a high specific energy and energy density. Further on, they are operational over a wide temperature range, show a flat discharge curve and provide good shelf life.

Table 7-1: Comparison between different available primary battery types. Based on [122].

System	Voltage	Specific energy (gravimetric)	Power density	Flat discharge profile	Low temperature operation	High temperature operation	Shelf life	Cost
Zinc / carbon	5	4	4	4	5	6	8	1
Zinc / alkaline / manganese dioxide	5	3	2	3	4	4	7	2
Magnesium / manganese dioxide	3	3	2	2	4	3	4	3
Zinc / silver oxide	4	3	2	2	4	3	5	6
Lithium / soluble cathode	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	5
Lithium / solid cathode	1	1	1	2	2	3	2	3

Table 7-2: Properties of different lithium-based primary cells. Based on [122].

Cell classification	System	Construction	Voltage [V]	Specific energy [Wh/kg]	Power density	Discharge profile	Available sizes [Ah]
Soluble cathode	Li/SO ₂	Spiral	3.0	260	High	Very flat	≤ 34
	Li/ SOCl ₂	Spiral	3.6	495	Medium	Flat	Cylindrical: 1.2-14 Flat disk: ≤ 2300
	Li/ SO ₂ Cl ₂	Spiral	3.9	485	Medium	Flat	2-30
Solid cathode	Li/ FeS ₂	Spiral	1.5	310	Medium to High	High initial drop, then flat	≤ 3.1
	Li/MnO ₂	Spiral	3.0	261	Medium to high	Moderately flat	≤ 11

7.1.3 Secondary Batteries

The following section describes the state-of-the-art of secondary batteries according to [122], [123] and [124].

Table 7-3 shows a comparison of common secondary battery systems according to [122]. Zinc/silver oxide, cadmium/silver oxide and nickel hydrogen systems have been excluded from the report due to their high costs.

Lead-acid systems are by far the least costly of all secondary batteries. Additionally, they exhibit a high cell voltage, efficiency over 70% and moderately good low temperature performance. The disadvantages of this technology are a low specific energy as well as a relatively short cycle life. Lead-acid batteries have been used in SPIDER [125] and BOOMERanG [73].

Table 7-3: Comparison of common secondary battery systems. Based on [122].

Battery System		Cell Voltage [V]	Temperature		Specific energy [Wh/kg]	Power density	Discharge profile	Efficiency		Self-discharge at 20°C [%/month]	Cycle life
			Operating [°C]	Charging [°C]				Ah [%]	Wh [%]		
Lead-acid	SLI	2.0	-40-55	-40-50	40	High	Flat	90	75	Sb-Pb: 20-30 Maint. free: 2-3	200-700
	Traction	2.0	-20-40	-40-50	25	Moderately high	Flat	80-90	70-75	4-6	1,500
	Stationary	2.0	-10-40	-40-50	10-20	Moderately high	Flat	80-90	70-75		
	Portable	2.0	-40-60	-40-50	30	High	Flat	80-90	70-75	4-8	250-500
Nickel-cadmium (Ni/Cd)	Pocket	1.2	-20-45	-50-40	27	High	Flat	70	60	5	500-2,000
	Sintered	1.2	-40-50	-55-75	30-37	High	Very flat	70-80	60-70	10	500-2,000
	Sealed	1.2	-20-70	0-40	35	Moderately high	Very flat	65-70	55-65	15-20	300-1,000
	FNC	1.2	-50-60		10-40	Very High	Flat			10-15	500-10,000
Nickel- zinc (Ni/Zn)	1.65	-20-50	-20-40	Prismatic: 60-100 Cylindrical: 70-110	High	Flat	85	70	20	900	
Nickel/ metal hydride (Ni/MH)	1.2	-20-65	0-40	90-110	High	Flat	65-70	55-65	15-30	500-1,000	
Lithium Ion	4.0	-20-50	0-50	203	Moderate/ High	Sloping	99	95	2	1,000+	
Zinc/ manganese dioxid (Zn/MnO ₂)	1.5	-20-40	10-30	100	Moderate	Sloping		55-65		15-25	

7.1.4 Solar Panels

The following section presents the current state-of-the-art efficiencies of solar panels as published by Green et al. [126]. The values listed in Table 7-4 are measured under the global AM 1.5 condition (air mass = 1.5, i.e. 48.2 deg Zenith angle, resulting in 1000 W/m² irradiance) at a cell temperature of 25°C. Only modules with an area larger than 800 cm² have been considered. All measurements must have been independently conducted by a recognized test center listed in Green et al. [127] to be included in this table.

Multi-Junction Gallium-Arsenide (MJ-GaAs) solar panels show the highest efficiency. Additionally, they exhibit much better performance in comparison to silicon solar panels. The main drawback of MJ-GaAs is their price. The cost to make a wafer of gallium arsenide is by a factor of ≈1,000 higher than for silicon. Therefore, the use of gallium arsenide solar panels is currently limited to applications that justify the higher price. This is the case for most space-borne applications, due to the high costs of a rocket launch.

Table 7-4: Current state-of-the-art efficiencies achieved by solar panels made from different substrates.

All measurements were done at independent recognized test centers. Module efficiencies were measured under the global AM1.5 spectrum (1000 W/m²) at a cell temperature of 25 °C (IEC 60904-3: 2008, ASTM G-173-03 global). Table was taken in abridged form from Green et al. (2017) [126]; see this reference more details.

Solar Cell Classification	Efficiency (%)	Area (cm ²)	V _{oc} (V)	I _{sc} (A)	FF (%)	Tested (mm/yr)	Manufacturer
Single-Junction							
Si (crystalline)	24.4 ± 0.5	13 177 (da)	79.5	5.04	80.1	09/2016	Kaneka (108 cells)
Si (multicrystalline)	19.9 ± 0.4	15 143 (ap)	78.87	4.795	79.5	10/2016	Trina Solar (120 cells)
GaAs (thin film)	24.1 ± 1.0	858.5 (ap)	10.89	2.255	84.2	11/2012	Alta Devices
CdTe (thin-film)	18.6 ± 0.6	7038.8 (ap)	110.6	1.533	74.2	04/2015	First Solar, monolithic
CIGS (Cd free)	17.5 ± 0.5	808 (da)	47.6	0.408	72.8	06/2014	Solar Frontier (70 cells)
CIGS (large)	15.7 ± 0.5	9703 (ap)	28.24	7.254	72.5	11/2010	Miasole
a-Si/nc-Si (tandem)	12.3 ± 0.3	14 322 (t)	280.1	0.902	69.9	09/2014	TEL Solar, Trubbach Labs
Organic	8.7 ± 0.3*	802 (da)	17.47	0.569	70.4	05/2014	Toshiba
Multi-Junction							
InGaP/GaAs/InGaAs	31.2 ± 1.2	968 (da)	23.95	1.506	83.6	02/2016	Sharp (32 cells)

Notes: CIGSS, CuInGaSSe; a-Si, amorphous silicon/hydrogen alloy; a-SiGe, amorphous silicon/germanium/hydrogen alloy; nc-Si, nanocrystalline or microcrystalline silicon; (t), total area; (ap), aperture area; (da), designated illumination area; FF, fill factor; *Initial performance (not stabilised).

7.2 SUPPLIERS OF BATTERIES

7.2.1 Primary and Secondary Batteries for Aerospace Applications

Table 7-5 lists manufacturer of primary and secondary batteries for aerospace applications. Due to the limited number of suppliers that serve the aerospace market, the table also includes manufacturers outside the European Union.

Table 7-5: Manufacturer for batteries used in aerospace applications.

Company	Country	Primary Batteries						Secondary Batteries			Others
		Ag/ Zn	Li/ SOCl ₂	Li/ SO ₂	Li/ MnO ₂	Li/ CF _x	Thermal	Ni/ Cd	Ni/ H ₂	Li Ion	
Acme Aerospace Inc.	USA							X		X	•
Aerolithium	USA									X	•
BST Systems, Inc.	USA	X									•
Concorde Battery	USA									X	• Pb/Acid
EaglePicher Technologies, LLC.	USA	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	• Pb/Acid
Electrochem Corporate	USA							X		X	• Pb/Acid • Li Ion Polymer • Ni/MH
EnerSys	USA		X	X				X		X	• Pb/Acid • Li/SO ₂ Cl ₂ • Li/V ₂ O ₅
GS Yuasa	Japan									X	•
MarathonNorco Aerospace	USA							X			•
Saft SA	France	X	X	X	X			X		X	• Ag/Al

7.2.2 Industrial Secondary Batteries

Table 7-6 lists manufacturer of industrial secondary batteries located in member countries of the European Union (EU). This list does not aim to be complete, but gives a short overview of established suppliers. These batteries do not have a rating for aerospace applications.

Table 7-6: Suppliers of secondary batteries for industrial applications.

Company	Country	Secondary Batteries				
		Lead-Acid	Ni/Cd	Ni/MH	Ni/Zn	Li Ion
Banner Batterien	Austria	X				
FIAMM	Italy	X				
Hoppecke Batterien	Germany	X	X	X		X
MIDAC	Italy	X				X
Moll Batterien	Germany	X				
Rombat	Romania	X				
Saft	France		X	X		X
S.C.P.S.	France				X	
Systems Sunlight	Greece	X	X			
TAB	Slovenia	X				

7.2.3 Solar Panels

Table 7-7 displays a list of solar panel manufacturers located in member countries of the European Union (EU). This list does not claim to be complete, but gives a short overview. There are plenty of other solar panel manufacturers in the EU and all over the world. The manufacturers of the most efficient solar panels are listed in the efficiency table published by Green et al. [126] for each solar cell technology (see above). After a desired cell technology is selected, specific research on possible manufacturers and the specifications of their products has to be conducted.

Table 7-7: Suppliers of solar panels.

Company	Country	Solar Panel						
		Si (mono-crystalline)	Si (poly-crystalline)	Si (thin film)	GaAs (thin film)	CdTe (thin film)	CIGS	TJ-GaAs
AE Solar	Germany	X	X					
Aleo Solar	Germany	X	X					
Avancis	Germany						X	
Azur Space Solar Power	Germany	X						X
Bosch	Germany	X	X	X				
Calyxo	Germany					X		
CESI	Italy							X
CTF Solar	Germany					X		
DHV Technology	Spain							X
Europe Solar Production	Norway	X	X					
Photowatt	France	X	X					
Renewable Energy Corporation	Norway		X					
Solarday	Italy	X	X					
Soluxtec	Luxembourg	X	X					
Tamesol	Spain	X	X					

[KS2]

Appendix 1. NAL Research Corporation Iridium SBD/Dial-Up Data / RUDICS Airtime Plans

Source: <http://www.nalresearch.com/Airtime.html>

Retrieved: 2017-05-05

Service	SBD Standard	SBD Fixed-Cost	Dial-Up Data	RUDICS
Monthly Subscription	\$13	\$16	\$14	\$14
SIM Card	\$10	\$10	\$10	\$10
Activation	\$700	\$740	\$30	\$2530
Data included	-	12 kbyte	-	-
First 30 bytes	\$0.04	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
After 30 bytes/included data	\$0.0015/byte	\$0.0015/byte	n.a.	n.a.
Cost/minute of connection	n.a.	n.a.	\$0.92	\$0.64

Appendix 2. Mailasail Iridium OpenPort Airtime Plans

Source: <http://www.mailasail.com/Communication/Iridium-Pilot-Airtime>

Retrieved: 2017-04-28

A2.1 Data Only Bundles

Choose from the following price plans (all plans have a one month minimum contract period). Voice calls not included in these bundles (charged in addition at standard rates):

A2.2 128 Kbps Max. Speed

Option	0 MB	10 MB	25 MB	75 MB	200 MB	1,000 MB	5,000 MB
Monthly Subscription	\$48.30	\$110.40	\$196.65	\$388.13	\$655.50	\$1,276.50	\$2,622.00
In Allowance - Implied Cost / MB	n/a	\$11.04	\$7.87	\$5.18	\$3.28	\$1.28	\$0.52
Out of Allowance – IP / MB	\$13.80	\$11.39	\$8.21	\$5.52	\$3.59	\$0.62	\$0.48

A2.3 64 Kbps Max. Speed

Option	0 MB	10 MB	25 MB	75 MB	200 MB	1,000 MB	5,000 MB
Monthly Subscription		\$104.88	\$186.82	\$368.72	\$622.73	\$1,212.68	\$2,490.90
In Allowance - Implied Cost / MB		\$10.48	\$7.47	\$4.92	\$3.11	\$1.21	\$0.50
Out of Allowance IP / MB		\$10.82	\$7.80	\$5.24	\$3.41	\$0.59	\$0.46

A2.4 64 Kbps Max. Speed

Option	0 MB	10 MB	25 MB	75 MB	200 MB	1,000 MB	5,000 MB
Monthly Subscription		\$99.36	\$176.99	\$349.31	\$589.95	\$1,148.85	\$2,359.80
In Allowance - Implied Cost / MB		\$9.94	\$7.08	\$4.66	\$2.95	\$1.15	\$0.47
Out of Allowance IP / MB		\$10.25	\$7.39	\$4.97	\$3.23	\$0.56	\$0.43

Appendix 3. Mailasail Inmarsat FleetBroadband Airtime

Source: <http://www.mailasail.com/Communication/Inmarsat-FleetBroadband-Airtime>

Retrieved: 2017-04-28

A3.1 Inmarsat FleetBroadband Airtime

Plan	Monthly Subscription	MB's Included	Mins Included	MB Rate ^{uuu}	Minimum Duration
Standard	\$457.50	25	n/a	\$18.30/MB	1 month
75MB	\$823.50	75	n/a	\$10.98/MB	12 months
250MB (2016)	\$1,372.50	250	n/a	\$5.49/MB	12 months
1GB	\$1,784.25	1,024	n/a	\$1.74 /MB	12 months
4GB	\$2,196.00	4,096	n/a	\$0.53/MB	24 months
8GB	\$2,928.00	8,192	n/a	\$0.37/MB	24 months
20GB	\$3,843.00	20,480	n/a	\$0.18/MB	24 months
40GB	\$5,124.00	40,960	n/a	\$0.13/MB	24 months

A3.2 Rates

Plan	Voice to Fixed	Voice to Cellular	Voice to BGAN/FB/SB/Voicemail (per min)	SMS (per msg)
Standard	\$0.70	\$0.97	\$0.70	\$0.46
1GB	\$0.44	\$0.62	\$0.44	\$0.24
4/8/20/40GB/unlimited	\$0.38	\$0.53	\$0.38	\$0.16

^{uuu} According to one time cost & included data volume. Additional data usage exceeding the included data volume is not foreseen. To obtain more data for short-term usage, several packages can be bought for the same time period (e.g. 3 “standard” packages adding up to 75 MB within the same month)

Appendix 4. Ground Control InmarSat BGAN Prepaid Service Plans

Source: http://www.groundcontrol.com/BGAN_rate_plans.htm

Retrieved: 2017-05-02

A4.1 InmarSat BGAN Prepaid Service Plans / SIM Cards

Plan	One time cost	Monthly Subscription	MB's included	MB Rate ^{vvv}	Validity
100 MB	\$525	0	100	\$5.25/MB	90 days
200 MB	\$995	0	200	\$4.97/MB	90 days
300 MB	\$1,467	0	300	\$4.89/MB	1 year
600 MB	\$2,820	0	600	\$4.70/MB	1 year
1200 MB	\$5,639	0	1,200	\$4.70/MB	1 year
2 GB	\$9,360	0	2,000	\$4.68/MB	1 year
3 GB	\$13,980	0	3,000	\$4.66/MB	1 year
4 GB	\$18,560	0	4,000	\$4.64/MB	1 year
5 GB	\$23,100	0	5,000	\$4.62/MB	1 year
7 GB	\$32,060	0	7,000	\$4.58/MB	1 year
10 GB	\$41,300	0	10,000	\$4.13/MB	1 year
15 GB	\$61,200	0	15,000	\$4.08/MB	1 year
25 GB	\$77,826	0	25,000	\$3.11/MB	1 year

^{vvv} According to one time cost & included data volume

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